

DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM FOR THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CAD	Computer-aided Design
CAD	Computer-aided Engineering.
CAM	Computer-aided Manufacturing
DFG	Digital Focus Groups
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LLM	Large Language Model
VR	Virtual Reality

Keywords

Digital solutions; Digital Focus Group; Miro board; NEB Prize winners; Education and training; AI literacy; Production and construction; Design & architecture.

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● Executive summary

In order to map the digitalisation trends across the NEB sector, to identify gaps, and put forward policy recommendations, five digital focus groups were organised, bringing in expert views from across the NEB landscape in a cross-sectional and multi-country approach. The qualitative input collection was preceded by desk research, which was also used in a continuous loop approach for refining, analysing, and interpreting results. Based on information saturation, key trends and common challenges were identified, presenting a comprehensive and up-to-date picture of the New European Bauhaus digitalisation status.

Digitalisation is driven by both push and pull factors, including the optimisation of processes and results (pull factors) and legislative requirements (push factors). Levels of digitalisation are high within the professional sector. There appears to be a correlation between the size of the organisation and the sector, and the maturity of the digitalisation profile. In the case of client- or citizen-facing processes and activities, the choice of digital solutions is influenced by the literacy level of the population, with age being correlated with levels of digital literacy.

Digitalisation should be a conscious choice and not a top-down imposition, as experienced by some participants. Analogue alternatives should be available for those unable or unwilling to adopt certain digital solutions. The myriad of alternative digital solutions leads to a time-consuming activity of selecting the suitable one. An interactive instrument allowing for comparison and facilitating choice between alternative digital solutions is highly needed. Non-intrusive digital solutions that can be seamlessly integrated or deployed for mapping the natural, traditional landscape are also needed.

There is a hype around AI, which is perceived as having negative consequences for other high-priority topics. AI is changing the workplace and requires adequate training to avoid its pitfalls. It is not low AI literacy that is most risky, but rather overconfidence in AI systems or overestimation of one's AI literacy and skills, leading to uncritical use of AI-provided output. This is particularly risky in the educational sector, where the embedding of AI applications changes the learning process and risks eliminating formative learning experiences. The educational sector is diverse regarding the integration of digital instruments, with academics expressing the view that digital poverty during the academic experience carries over into professional life. The speed of technological development also puts pressure on trainers who need to acquire new skills quickly. The development of digital skills needs to be embedded in a contextualised learning experience and should not be an objective in itself.

The adoption of bio-based materials is influenced by cost, perception, traditions, and the lack of standards and the possibility to insure constructions made from these materials. There is a perceived lack of education and training materials regarding the use of bio-based materials.

A high volume of small-scale NEB initiatives leads to fragmentation and low visibility of the NEB programme among the wider population, missing out on the assumed capitalisation of broad community involvement. Digitalisation is seen as an enabler for the Green Deal. Although wider geopolitical factors are acknowledged as having an impact on the Green Deal and digitalisation targets, they are not perceived as a main influencing factor, indicating that they are rather a focus for policy-level agendas.

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● Research objectives and expected outcomes

Deliverable D.2.5 summarises the activities conducted for and in connection with the Digital Focus Groups (DFGs), includes the landscape of the best practices in each field, the identified gaps and presents results from each field of analysis. The purpose of this exploratory research was to investigate the New European Bauhaus (NEB) priority topics, to collect input from NEB stakeholders on best practices and key challenges in the NEB community, to map the NEB landscape, identify overarching trends and gaps in the needed digital solutions, skills and knowledge that are needed to reach the objectives of the New European Bauhaus and the Green Deal. In line with the Description of Action, the collected input is meant to produce capacity-building materials, showcase identified best practice uses of digital technologies for the NEB, policy recommendations and a NEB Digital Deployment Roadmap. In order to reach the project objectives, a multilayered data collection activity was planned throughout 2024, involving stakeholders at different levels. The data collection included desk research and qualitative research activities. In the desk research phase, policies, case studies, and documentation were analysed in order to narrow down the topics of investigation and identify the main questions to be addressed in the qualitative data collection activity.

The present deliverable summarises the content of each Digital Focus Group, including the preliminary and subsequent desk research, supplementary individual (1x1) interviews and written collected input, best practices and recommendations from each field analysis. The input from the thematic Digital Focus Groups feeds into several deliverables and research outputs:

- D.2.5 Landscape report and gap analysis.
- D.5.3 DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap.
- Research output disseminated in the Open Research Europe platform in the form of position papers planned for the Digital Focus Groups part of WP2.

The research methodology and research design are detailed in the following sections.

- Research design and methodology

Given the breadth of the New European Bauhaus programme, the research followed a funnel model, starting with the identification of macro areas and topics of priority for the NEB community around the themes of digitalization and the European Green Deal. This initial exploratory research phase is represented in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Design of the exploratory research phase

Throughout the investigation phase of the project, this desk research activity was continuous, feeding back into the instruments used for qualitative data collection and refinement and interpretation of results. Data collection was undertaken through different methods, including desk research, focus group activities, individual interviews and input collection through participation in multiplier and dissemination events, presented on Figure 2.

Fig.2. Types of data collection activities

In line with the DOA, the Technical Working Groups, renamed as Digital Focus Groups in the project amendments, were organised to address specific macro areas and topics of priority, collect input from stakeholders and key experts and facilitate the gap analysis. The focus group questionnaire was developed based on desk research incorporating best practices case studies, official NEB documents (Horizon Europe, 2024; European Commission, 2024 a.; 2023). The Digital Focus Groups (DFGs) were planned as online 90 minutes long activities. The Digital Focus Groups were conducted via Teams and included a Miro Board exercise for collecting written, structured input in a creative, interactive manner. This was done in order to apply the NEB principles: Beautiful - Sustainable – Together, and to better engage the participants who are professionals with a strong design orientation. The outputs of the Miro Boards are presented in the data analysis section of each DFG and the Annexes of the present deliverable.

Approvals for research involving human participants were sought, based on documentation including a data management plan, ethics checklist and informed consent forms, in line with the policies of the Project Coordinator, Delft University of Technology.

Participants in the Digital Focus Groups included professionals from the NEB community, government officials, educators, key experts and actors in the sector from different member states and institutions, representatives from professional communities and professional associations within the broader New European Bauhaus community, internal stakeholders, such as the members of the Early Adaptors Board, members affiliated to the professional associations who are project partners, external stakeholders, professionals with a background in early and visible adaption of digital solutions, civic engagement representatives. Participants were recruited based on initial desk research on the representative stakeholders for the NEB community and NEB programme and subsequent snowball sampling, aiming for geographical distribution of opinions. The need for a qualitative rather than quantitative approach to the investigation was multi fold, and motivated by:

- the extent of the NEB programme across different EU member states and associated countries;
- the diversity of the topics within the programme;
- the diversity of scale of the actors that are relevant for the NEB;
- the novelty of emerging disruptive trends manifesting themselves in the NEB, such as the use of AI that required an exploratory approach at first.
- Other cross-dissemination/ recruitment strategies included call for participation through:
 - the NEB newsletter through the European contact point for NEB;
 - the European Commission’s NEB community platform calendar of events;
 - presentation given in the European Federation for Living Social Topic Group;
 - the TU Delft AI initiative.

The desk research was conducted in a continuous manner and incorporated in research outputs and deliverables, reflecting the dynamic of the digitalisation and AI landscape throughout 2024. One of the biggest challenges was keeping track of the sheer amount of outputs dedicated to AI and existing different scale AI initiatives scattered throughout the NEB landscape and incorporating them in the research analysis and outputs and project deliverables.

The above-presented data collection activities were not linear, with the exception of the phase for establishing and refining the interview questions for the thematic focus groups. In response to the observation of a disruptive technological trend within the NEB – namely the upcoming of AI - an additional two-part workshop on AI, focusing on AI literacy and risks and values around AI systems was included and conducted, capitalizing on the momentum that AI applications have both in the practice field and in the EU environment at the moment, given the overlap of the adoption and beginning of the implementation of the EU AI Act with the second year of the DigiNEB project, the newly formed EU AI Office, and the activities of the European Centre for Algorithmic Transparency. Seen as part of the digitalisation trend in the NEB community, the research activity around AI showcases the attention volume and weight that the technology receives in the user’s community and NEB professionals. The digital technical group on AI was organised in a multilayered approach. Because of its size and topicality, it is being disseminated as a standalone article entitled “Critical exploratory investigation of AI consumption, AI perception and AI literacy requirements alignment”. The AI data collection activity followed a multilevel collection plan, detailed in the corresponding methodological section dedicated to the subchapter.

Additional discussions with experts were held in order to capture the views of key stakeholders who could not join the group discussions due to agenda conflicts and to accommodate relevant niche perspectives and as a form of stakeholder engagement. On the whole, the participants included in the investigation represented a sample of opportunity, aimed at capturing the diversity of perspectives of the NEB programme. The results of the analysis thus reflect the diversity of perspectives across the NEB and in the same time identify visible, consistent trends based on information saturation. To reach the desired number of participants, an initial sample of 3 times the number of desired participants was aimed for. As such, an average of 20 invitations were sent for each DFG, to NEB members from EU member states and associated countries. The Digital Focus Groups were thus complemented by additional data collection through 1x1 expert discussions, desk research and participation and interactions during dissemination or multiplier events. After multiple rounds of information collection and the DFG, information saturation was reached. The results of the research therefore represent a credible picture at the present moment of the NEB landscape regarding perceptions of the programme, the use of digital solutions and shared challenges regarding their use.

Fig.3. Presentation of the DigiNEB project during the DFG

The discussions during the Digital Focus Groups surpassed the initially allocated time, as a result of the exchange of opinions, complexity and details of the answers. Several cross-themes were identified in the Digital Focus Groups that are presented and analysed.

- 1.1 Digital Focus Group - civic engagement/ NEB winners

The Digital Focus Group with the NEB prize winners and representatives of civic organisations comprised 9 participants attending the online working group from the following member states and associated countries: Italy, Belgium, Portugal, Lithuania, France, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. During the discussion, the participants expressed agreement with points made previously by other participants in the group, indicating shared experiences. Participants included representatives of large housing providers and the housing sector, European umbrella organisations in the (social) housing sector, organisations active in the area of repurposing and recovery of materials and social inclusion (such as organisations employing refugees and asylum seekers), leaders of winning digital projects dedicated to civic involvement, NGOs, researchers that were winners of NEB projects and civil society organisation winners of NEB projects. Typical of umbrella organisations, participants were also wearing multiple hats and, during the discussion, shared experiences from different member states, having transnational professional experiences.

■ 1.1.2 Main digitalisation challenges

Digitalisation doesn't come only with perks but also poses challenges: “[...] in terms of how we are being digital, I think sometimes there are opportunities, but also sometimes we're hobbled by the kind of systems that we have as an organization”. Referring to digital solutions of large service providers, respondents mentioned their functionalities as well as to their constraints, making tracking end-to-end customer journey difficult.

Innovation in silos is another challenge referred to by respondents: “there are [...] pockets of innovation, but they often happen in [...] discreet/small parts of the business”. The fact that innovation takes place in “corners” of the business is not in itself a negative aspect, as there might be more time and room for testing alternative, innovative solution in non-core processes. The implicit negative appreciation of this fact is that there is no subsequent uptake of that innovation throughout the organisation. This has to do then not with the digital solutions themselves, but most likely with costs associated with changing of existing processes, methods and solutions throughout the organisation, the compatibility of those innovative solutions with others that might come from large hyperscale providers that offer the referred-to added functionalities. Two connected challenges are attracting the needed digital savvy human resources and the integration of the “discrete innovation” in the mainstream or so-called *business as usual* processes: “how do we integrate this great tech with the probably substandard property and customer systems that we have?”

The competition for resources takes place within the sector but also across sectors, becoming a particular challenge for the civil society that struggles to attract and retain human resources with the needed digital skills: “competing with private sector organizations for those skills [...] gets very expensive and sometimes you might not always attract the best people into those roles”. Skills are not the only scarce resource that industry, academia or civil society have to fight and compete for, but also the materials needed by the sector, as detailed in the next section.

A difference was noted regarding the digital solutions exclusively or predominantly used by the professional community and those deployed by the representatives of the housing sector in order to interact with their clients, inhabitants of the lived space or citizens. As civil society organisations, housing corporations interact with different environments and target groups, a new issue emerges: that of the gap between the digital tools used by these deployers and the level of digitalisation in which the deployment is tented. Participants report prioritizing the characteristics of the environment and the target group to that of their own (digital) practices: “we encourage real relationships not virtual relationships”. If participatory processes experienced during professional activities were mostly positively appreciated (with concrete examples from the United Kingdom and Scotland), the interaction between professionals and the citizens is what presents a challenge in terms of a mismatch of technology readiness or adoption willingness. Reflecting the intersectionality character of the housing sector and inclusion services, respondents address the issue of the “20% of residents that are not online” and therefore housing corporations have to also provide analogue solutions in order to accommodate their requirements: “we can't always [...] be digital by default”. Digital solutions specifically dedicated to the aging populations are needed, on the backdrop of this broader European phenomenon. A low barrier example in this regard is the digitalisation of the public space in order to engage citizen by means of placing QR codes in public spaces to encourage digital inclusion and interaction and digital regeneration. This topic of digital solutions adapted to the aging population trend also comes back while discussing AI usage and its risks by elderly individuals, as detailed in subsequent sections.

Another participant from a social housing corporation in Italy mentioned that digitalisation in itself is not a requirement: the technically required software for the construction sector are available, but when it comes to digital tools to get people involved in the design and process phases

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“we're still a little bit far back” and the challenge is how “to get technologies and digitalization involved in order to get to more to a bigger audience”. Therefore, the characteristics of the target group of a certain initiative or programme must be the starting point for determining the ways in which the objectives must be reached, also in terms of the digital solution used. Respondents give the example of older residents in social housing buildings who are difficult to reach even by email and in such cases, the attempted deployment of technology is not considered to bring added benefits: “I think what you have to bear in mind is always the target and the people you're talking to and starting from that, maybe you have a sort of different scenarios you can choose from. And then according to that scenario, you choose which digital tool, which technology could be more appropriate”.

Digitalisation also seems to be happening by force for some practitioners: participants who define themselves as designers mention having avoided the digital as much as possible but no little avail. This idea of digitalisation by choice not by compulsion is repeated by other participants: “suggest and not impose digital tools”; “I see a lot of call for projects, for instance, that impose the use of digital tools and that are not just suggesting and some sometimes it's really hard for an organization to answer sometimes because digitalization, digitalized tools are imposed.” Digitalisation initiatives should therefore be sustained by a natural update and not enforced by in environments that are not suited for digitalisation or are impermeable, for different reasons, to it.

■ 1.1.3 Digital solution most needed at the moment

Digitalisation is not experienced homogeneously or amorphously. Rather than being used just as a medium, it is also experienced in a more holistic way. A respondent reported on their own project in the following terms: “our project [...] is actually quite interesting in terms of digitalization, because the goal was to use the digital tools to inform the physicality of it, which is highly driven by living organisms. [...] We are working on more directions of integrative design through the prism of extremes and that's understood quite widely. And that involves any kind of biomaterials, any kind of bio design relation [...], but also sustainability in general, systems thinking”. The idea of system thinking was picked up and expanded by another speaker, suggesting an integrated solution including the effects of the built environment on the living environment:

“Post occupancy evaluation. It is a field in which many different methodologies are applied. [Mostly] are qualitative research methodologies, such as interviews. People go on a survey and try to understand which are the issues or the good points of a building. How is life in a building? [...] this could be more [in the form] of a system. I think of my office where we have different buildings and they have obviously their own peculiarities and their communities that make life inside them different. What about having a system that somehow is helped by the digital platform where you can also compare what happens and what people say after they start living inside a building? So, the effect of the buildings on people and the other way around as well. What could be improved according to what people say and what people need?”.

In addition to this complex post-occupancy continuous evaluation platform, digital solutions giving insight into the energy efficiency needs of existing buildings are welcomed.

In small scale creative, artisanal initiatives, both digital tools such as Rhino and manual labour are used next to each other, and additional digital solutions are welcome to replace the second: “We still have a long way to go to develop certain things”. A desired digital tool for this respondent is a time, resources and cost quantifying tool for the manual labour and products used, thus a digital solution that would capture every stage of the product life cycle, the cost and resources: “Something [that allows] the artisan to understand the cost of each product itself. So the time it requires, [...] noting down exactly the time, the materials this work requires, the quantity of time, the weight of all the products that we create. So we keep track of that and we're trying to keep track of more and more

things in order to understand more about our projects as well in a certain sense. I think that would be a tool that would be useful for us”.

Another participant mentioned the need for a digital solution to measure impact for biosynthesized materials and of other elements that are not measured in terms of impact: a “digital tool that could help to establish that measurement, help them compare and also be more economically viable in that sense.” New digital solutions and standardisation are needed in relation to new materials: “A lot of these so-called novel materials are blocked by certification and this kind of lack of standardization to certain extent. And they're basically pushed into the categories of concrete or bricks and it's a bit problematic because they are not really the same category”. Lacking solutions are thus not only of technical nature but also of regulatory nature.

Developing solutions that look at end of the life cycle of products and map the impact of these processes are also needed. This is relevant for the material recovering and repurposing processes. Having catalogue of materials and solutions, their temporal characteristics, repurposing capacity, real life application and impact is needed. This is also connected to the lack of a clear overview of existing solutions also leads to duplication of efforts and the sentiment of “reinventing the wheel”. Catalogues involving current and possible new purposes of materials are referred to by participants, but they are also characterized as not being mature enough. A material-focused database is welcome, including a comparison of different results of what people achieved. At the same time, different industries compete over these finite resources or materials, and different budgets have an impact on certification ability: “blocking certification slows everything down”. Standardization is difficult to achieve, so focusing instead on what is achievable would be a step further.

Another digital solution that is mentioned to be lacking and that is desired is one being able to collaborative map heritage and ancient crafts in natural environments:

“I worked recently in a village where ancient crafts were being forgotten, and so the collective there was trying to build an archive of this heritage. And there the digitalization was very interesting because it allowed different residents at different times to map some discoveries or some archival materials. So to find a way to map in a way that it's sensible, that is actually quite human. Being collaborative could bring a lot accessible knowledge on a living environment like a forest or a village community.”

Integrating the digital in the living environment as seamlessly as possible while being as inclusive as possible is another challenge. Often, digitalisation initiatives are developed to improve digitalisation levels of already (to different extents) digital spaces. Digitalisation needs are not limited to the traditional build environment. According to participants, there is a lot of accessible knowledge in the living environment, like forests, villages and communities. In the case of natural heritage sites, the effect that digitalisation has on the natural environment must be part of the impact evaluation of implementing digital solutions, together with the need to best accommodate the local community needs. Data collection in this setting faces the challenge of being accessible for anyone to participate in the mapping and that “involves devices that are not so intimidating as computers or some kind of mediator. [...] Make it digital and available worldwide”. For this setting, required characteristics of the digital tool are user design and “humanness” of the digital tool. The mapping suggestion received wide group support in the subsequent interventions and was expanded upon by several participants: “I'm liking what I'm hearing at the moment about kind of mapping impacts and understanding different needs and experiences as well.”

■ 1.1.4 Use of AI solutions

The activities for which AI can be used were also discussed, including: data collection or data analysis, AI as enabler of a smart, learning environment, deployed as solution for addressing the

problem of the aging of the population increasing care needs. Respondents mentioned not having a clear (i.e. exhaustive) picture of how AI is used in their sector at the moment, but mentioned training and dissemination initiatives on AI.

AI is used for facilitating citizen engagement in the decision-making process. A project involving a large French housing provider is referenced as an example of use of VR in combination with AI to raise resident involvement in the project for the new construction and give residents a clear idea of what the future site will look like. AI and VR are also used to gain support for renovation projects “because given the high housing crisis in all Europe, many times projects area blocked by a resident involvement. It becomes very important to give people who are. in a way, hit or affected by development a say in the new construction or within the existing buildings”.

The robotisation and AI integrated solutions trends taking place in the housing sector and in the care sector are closely being monitored as possible solutions for the challenges brought forward by changing demographics and the trend of aging population taking place across Europe. These solutions are especially important in the South of Europe, Italy, France, Finland, in the Scandinavian countries, and, in the view of respondents, less so in Eastern Europe where the population is comparatively younger. Another participant from Italy reported on the activity of a working group on AI around disability and inclusivity, mentioning that more research is needed on when to use AI. A reported experience was that of an elderly person mentioning not liking to interact with digital tools “because I cannot say thank you”, a perspective which struck the respondent of the DFG as being unexpected. One other observation here is the fact that both of the mentioned cases reporting on experiences of elderly persons interacting with AI are from Italy, which aligns with the perspective mentioned earlier by one of the participants on the ageing of the population in Southern and Northern Europe. AI is also becoming part of the individual lived environment, the home, as interactive intermediary (adapting the indoor climate etc.) but it can also be deployed for specific groups with specific needs, such as vulnerable people, in order to better care for their needs while inside the home. This implementation of smart solutions inside the home for care purposes is not new, with smart systems such as sensors for detection of a person having fallen and not moving sending automatic call to emergency services being already implemented in homes in the Netherlands for example. Digital solutions implemented in the home could thus help elderly persons remain for longer in their own home, and have an independent life instead of having to live in a care facility. As counter story, another participant reported on the perspective of young students interacting with AI, which was characterized as “scary” due to an accompanying lack of critical inquiry into the results the AI produces: “with the young people that haven't really developed certain skills yet or they haven't and they didn't train their eye and maybe in the case of the design they haven't seen enough example, they haven't went through a lot of studies, they haven't read a lot or they haven't written a lot. [it's becoming dangerous].” The example provided by the participant to emphasise this aspect is the usage by students of an AI enabled output representing Iceland as an ice land image. Respondents suggest that universities should address this gap in their educational programmes. This gap in the existing educational programmes regarding the critical usage of AI and critical interpretation of its outputs was recurrent throughout the Digital Focus Groups.

This literacy requirement is not limited to the formal educational sector. It was observed by a participant from the creative sector from Italy that there is an increased trend in AI attention, coupled by a sense of fear. This aligns with the perspective expressed by the participants in the AI-dedicated literacy workshop and provocation activity, detailed in subchapter 3. This sense of fear might stream from low AI literacy leading to little understanding of how the system works and fearing the mediatized impact AI has on the job market. Participants also observe that “there hasn't been enough education about it”. This low literacy can become a risk. Interestingly enough, it is not low literacy in absolute terms that presents the highest risk, but as respondents note, it is the

unfunded belief that there is a certain degree of AI literacy that is more risky: “There are obviously people who are investing their time in and learning how to use it, but there are also these cases where it is not done in such a way and where I find that it's in a certain sense a dangerous tool, especially for older people, the elderly, who are not familiar with this tool”.

If in the case of professionals, [individuals with mature work experience], the use of AI speeds up and shortens certain processes, therefore having concrete benefits, in the case of young adults using AI, the difference in accumulated experiences influences patterns of critical consumption. The assumption here is that unexperienced users are much less critical of the results before using them and the result is that reliance on “ready-made” outputs has a negative impact on the critical thinking capacity of young individuals. Usage of these ready-made products, while at the same time not having sufficient accumulated knowledge or experience from long-term intellect developing activities such as reading and writing has a continuous negative effect on the critical thinking ability, finds the respondent. Another challenge associated with AI is that its continuous use has an exponential growth effect of its results, multiplying the results it previously produced. The true creative character of the results that are produced by this usage is questioned. Repeated usage and reliance on AI systems hinders the development of new (creative) knowledge.

Fig. 6. Quotes from the DFG on civic engagement

■ 1.1.2 Visibility and priorities of the NEB programme

Asked what should be the priorities of the new NEB programme, respondents made references to the low visibility and fragmentation of the programme: “[...] the NEB, although it's meant for [...] the large number of people living in Europe [...] in many countries it's still hardly known, it's still in my view an organization of networks or people within the sector, architects, the housing sector, design sector.” The scale of the projects included in the NEB is put in relation with the programme's low visibility and connected with the need for a more efficient use of financial means: “there are sometimes some local initiatives and residents are involved, but it misses engagements with all the people living in the countries on a bigger level, because when you talk about enlarging the NEB, it is also about money. There is a discussion currently in the Netherlands about where the taxpayer money goes to”. Other participants added similar points of view: “Inspiring [NEB] projects [through Europe with] are difficult to connect” It is difficult to know each other and to know precisely the other initiative through Europe that we can connect with”.

Knowledge about the NEB is concentrated in the group of experts that are directly involved with the programme. Therefore: “the NEB needs more public attention. [...] We are experts, we are in the sector, we are invited via – via or by the EU and the Commission [but] people on the street don't know anything about it”. The NEB is still limited to an internal circle, ecosystem, not mentioned in the main news outlets. There is the perception that work is being done on the NEB at a political level but more attention is needed for the programme within the general public at national levels. The visibility of the NEB is very polarised: with top and bottom initiatives being active, but none for the middle, general audience. Better visibility of the programme and up scaling of projects are needed. That is key for the future. Making the goals of the NEB clearer was also mentioned by participants. People should be able to see how the NEB can change their lives, and projects with concrete results should be recognized and highlighted. Participants mention that the new European Commissioner on Housing is expected to embrace the NEB and that is considered a good starting point.

The winners of the NEB prizes expressed the desire for having an active community, as at the moment their interaction is facilitated only by a WhatsApp group. There is a perceived discrepancy between the way the NEB is advertising its membership as “a community” and the actual levels of interaction taking place, the latter being rather unidirectional in the sense of information flows from the programme administrators to the members in the form of newsletters. The need for an active NEB community has been stressed during the discussion: “Really promoting it in that way that there will be community would be super nice”. The NEB festival has a nice mixture of interesting people and integrating these people in the process of creating it would be beneficial.

A very easy way to get people to know each other from the beginning of the European Bauhaus prize [and integrate and keep them in the] NEB program, in its general aspects and activities is desired.

Participants also specifically wanted to send critical feedback about the programme, taking the opportunity of participating in the DFG to do so. Changing the voting platform for the NEB projects would be a great improvement to the digital presence of the NEB, due to its lack intuitiveness: “The interface of the NEB platform to me and to everyone that I've asked to vote for is completely dysfunctional.”. The information related to the NEB must be easier to read and in the same time be adapted to different audiences “for the younger people it must be interesting enough and for the older people it must be simple enough.” The messaging of the NEB platform was characterized as distant, not friendly and inaccessible. Better accessibility and focus on “the human touch” are needed for the message to reach the people. Functionalities addressing the needs of people with impairments should be embedded within the platform, given the declared focus on inclusiveness of the programme: “we're talking about inclusiveness and I haven't seen enough effort in community in

the communication of the New European Bauhaus”. These elements should be included in the communication strategy, choice of social media, fonts, background of the message being delivered. Another participant suggested including voice to text functionalities facilitated by AI to accommodate the needs of users with lower literacy levels. A last suggestion was to add the mapping the different actors of the NEB and the winners on the platform would make it easier to visualize what has been done and what’s happening in the network.

The results of the Miro Board interactive exercise are presented in the following section.

■ 1.1.3 Miro board results

Enablers of technological innovation

The identification of enablers of technological innovation was done in the form of an open question included in the written input collection in order to allow participants a longer response time. The answers included:

- Get people used to engaging with platforms to overcome barriers (e.g. Power BI);
- Shared tool box;
- Hardware and Software;
- alternative software to GAFAM;
- Training Programs;
- Partnerships and Collaboration;
- Continuous training;
- Start-up companies;
- Skills - both bringing these into the sector and upskilling people;
- Identify projects that would benefit from use of tech;
- Education/knowledge exchange chances (i.e. courses, seminars) to learn the opportunities out there and how to properly use these technologies;
- Diversity of materials and new functionalities in terms of bio-integration;
- NEB/EU guidelines with categories of tools to be used in different scenarios/targeted people;
- Interdisciplinarity - advancement through cross fields collaborations;
- Environmental requirements such as biodiversity credits.

Figure 7. Enablers of technological innovation. DFG: Neb prize winners and civic engagement.

The digitalisation needs that should be prioritized

The identification of digitalisation needs was designed in the form of a poll question. The included pre-determined options put under evaluation were identified in preliminary gap and landscape analysis on the status of the NEB, included in the previous DigiNEB project documents and deliverables.

These pre-determined digitalisation needs were:

- Platforms allowing collaboration on projects from any device with access to all project documents: contracts, RFIs, submittals, schedules, drawings and more.
- Clustered solutions allowing for creation of personalized unique functional work context and for tool combination.
- Communication;
- Digital solutions for material passports;
- Applications for citizen engagement;
- e-governance platforms.
- Recruiting
- Applications for citizen engagement
- Archiving
- Advanced materials

Figure 8. digitalisation needs that should be prioritized. DFG: Neb prize winners and civic engagement.

The digitalisation needs that were considered most stringent, as presented in Figure 8 were:

- Platforms allowing collaboration on projects from any device with access to all project documents: contracts, RFIs, submittals, schedules, drawings and more.
- Applications for citizen engagement.
- Communication.

In addition to the pre-determined options, participants were also given the opportunity to add other elements. Additional input provided by participants on this question included:

- Digital inclusion initiatives to help get the digitally excluded online
- Ageing and other demographic trends

Regarding existing platforms, one participant mentioned that there are at least two main categories: the professional. Power BI enabled ones used in daily activities by practitioners and the platforms that the customers or residents can access and collaborate on.

Main factors for open strategic autonomy

The factors included in the question of open strategic autonomy were extracted from formal EU polities in the area of the New European Bauhaus.

Figure 9. The main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe DFG: NEB prize winners and civic engagement.

Based on participants' evaluation of the main factors for strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe the factors with the highest relevance are:

- The growth of a circular and regenerative construction sector;
- Measures for increasing inclusiveness and democracy;
- The green transition.

Additional input included cost impacting on the sector, and how cost impacts competitiveness, suggesting that there should be less focus on policy and more on market drivers instead of policy drivers: “there's been a lot of inflation and building materials in the sector recently, but longer term, are we going to be charged for having poorly performing properties from a green perspective. [...] There's lots of different kind of cost pressures”.

Respondents were also asked about the digital skills needed for the realization of the objectives of the New European Bauhaus. Answers included insight and data that facilitate understanding of communities and neighbourhoods and the people living in them as simple data collection is not enough. For some types of data there is a consistent picture across Europe, however more diversity of areas of consistent data is needed, together with the necessary skills in order to make sense of the embedded patterns, such as the makeup and needs of communities, in order to determine best ways of interaction. The need for more collaborative skills in terms of interdisciplinarity was also mentioned and put in relation with the complex problems of climate change and the green transition.

built environment, and who, in the opinion of the respondent, are left out of the discussion: “in a professional context, how do we facilitate [...] engagement with the actual performance of the design intervention, whether at urban scale or the building scale and try to actually use digital tools as a means [...] of enable different stakeholders to engage with it”.

An example of useful digital solution is that of the digital twin, where a built or urban environment is created in which one can “keep track of the actual performance of a building, bringing in the data, the performance of it and then provides an interface with different kinds of stakeholders”. One respondent made references to experiences in the manufacturing sector, focusing on the life cycle management in the case of buildings. Similar to inputs provided in the civic engagement on the need for digital solutions dedicated to the end-of-life stage, respondents in this Digital Focus Group mention that the end-of-life phase can be facilitated by data driven technologies and by digital tools such as digital twins or artificially intelligence apps or Internet of Things.

Reporting from the double role of education and industry representative, a respondent mentioned that digital solutions for quantification and testing of objectives are needed: “In the context of sustainability in particular, what actually really matters is to know how effective our solutions are. We design buildings and claim it's sustainable or we're adapting historic buildings, claiming it's sustainable. We can make those claims, but what's really important is to be able to actually have the data to tell us that these measures are actually working and to my mind, the digital tool will play an enormously important role in that.”. VR is also used within the design process as it enables to visually critique designs and reduce the amount of money spent on physical models as part of the initial prototyping stage. This reduces the carbon footprint while visualizing in 3D and experiencing a space enables better decision making.

Another reported use of digital solutions reflects the facilitation of standardized procedures. Examples include the fire safety sector, where standards are developed to determine how biosafety information is communicated. Digital solutions for facilitating interactions around the actual performance of buildings are also mentioned.

A final remark regards the multiple functions that some of the professional tools can have, serving also as instruments for engagement with the wider public, for example by means of rendering sense to vast amounts of data through visualisation. This use is further detailed and commented in the section addressing digital solutions for engagement, included below.

■ 1.2.3 Digital skills, educational needs and challenges

Infrastructure available in educational institutions has an impact on present and future digital skills. Reporting from the perspective of the higher educational sector, digital poverty was mentioned as being one major issue having effects not only at “the T moment” while in the learning process but also later on, in the professional life. One might argue that digital poverty faced in a university can be overcome one in the professional sector, but undeniably, there will still be a start deficit for the students that face such deprivations. Digital poverty in higher education institutions thus affects the career chances of students:

“one big [challenge] in terms of the digitalisation landscape is the digital poverty side of things. If we take this all the way back to its grassroots, actually learning these tools in an academic context [faces the] problem that many of these software solutions require heavy computation to simulate various forms of kinds of building design and outputs, even if it's just calculating basic U values of a building or something. [...] A big problem there is that many of our students can't afford to purchase high-end laptops. Not all universities have high end equipment to learn on. [...] a big part of the problem is

taking this back to its grassroots and trying to find sustainable solutions early on that are more accessible to students, whether they're cloud based, whether they utilize AI, doesn't matter.”

Cost is a factor that influences levels of digitalisation: “the problems we've had in particularly post COVID is that many of the software vendors have drastically increased their prices of software.”. Examples in this regard included the Safira plugin for SketchUp used for building and sustainability design that from being a free plugin for calculating U values became a very expensive yearly purchase. These high costs for basic digital solutions become barriers for students who are thus deterred from learning about how to calculate sustainability as part of the design process and universities need to switch periodically between solutions depending on the fluctuating costs: “Every year we're having to pivot to whether it's Autodesk Inside, whether it's a bit of Sapphira, it might be some grasshopper tools in rhino. And I think that's one of the big barriers we're facing.”

Respondents report embedded skills for using digital tools in architecture curriculums at MA level “very deliberately”. These digital solutions are however embedded within the educational processes of acquiring of fundamental knowledge, becoming thus facilitating instruments or integral parts of a certain fundamental learning process, not a learning objective in themselves. One such example is building physics, where: “[one] needs really good grounding of the building physics to really understand what the tools are actually doing. Because it's quite easy to make the tools spit out certain data. If the user doesn't understand those data critically enough, they can become [...] misleading and problematic”. Again here, the message that comes across from the educational sector is that digitalisation in itself is not the purpose, and more consideration should be given to how these digital solutions give and receive meaning and added value in a knowledge acquiring or skill developing context.

Use of novel technology can increase interest of a certain target group (or) in a certain topic. In educational settings, the use of image capturing with the help of drones such as the Phantom 4 drone is reported: based on the captured imagery, students can afterwards experience the site in AR or VR without having to travel to the site. Additional layers of information can be then brought in as a form of exchange for interacting with the technology. The novelty, dynamic and interactive character of the technology increases engagement: “We tend to get the community engaged because everyone's very interested in the drone flying around and it's a very good opportunity for us to then get that client and [...] community engagement involved because they then want to put the headset on. They're interested in the technology and they're happy to then surrender some data for it”. Technology deployment in itself is not a panacea for lack of engagement, but rather it needs embedding within a narrative that transmits the enthusiasm and conviction over the benefits of technology deployment: “It's getting excitement in the community with the technology. It's not just saying here are some visuals or here is a model it's saying “look at what we're doing”. Look at this cutting-edge stuff that we can do, come and join in and people love it. People are really interested in it.”

Digitalisation increased knowledge complexity: “Modern tools are not necessarily making life easier, they are creating new capacities that we previously didn't have to make it possible to simulate building behaviours in a way that becomes incredibly more sophisticated than it has ever been”. This will presumably lead to narrower and narrower specialisation. The moment when and level at which this specialisation takes place are however debated. It was noted during the discussion that a structural change has taken place within the educational programmes where Bachelor level Architectural programmes shifted their focus from forming “traditional artworkers or CAD technicians to digital generalists”. This transformation has been internalised and is now being promoted explicitly: “by the end of our BA course, students will be able to produce technical drawings to British ISO standards, they might have an introduction to Revit. Probably just level one, maybe level 2, depending on the nature of the project and they will have some sustainability embedded within the curriculum as well. And then we also have the full suite of

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visualization. It could be anything from just renders, motion graphics, post production. Students, by the end of it will have touched on each of those skill sets and then they can branch out into any direction that they want to go into”.

The subject of education and training on AI was recurrent throughout all Digital Focus Groups. An additional issue identified in 1x1 interviews with representatives of the educational sector is the low skills levels of PhD students who apply for AI related vacancies and projects at European technical universities found at the forefront of the AI landscape. This indicates that skills and knowledge levels should be addressed much earlier in the educational programmes, in Bachelor or Master level programmes. Foreseen challenges of this endeavour are that this would translate into longer training programmes, or AI literacy would be introduced at the expense of other subjects. An additional motivation for more AI oriented educational programmes is that the skills found at local/regional level do not cover current market and research demands and there is a substantial difference in the education levels coming from outside the region. An additional challenge faced by the educational environment is that the format of the university trainings is usually small, seen the hands-on approach that is needed for learning how to use the technology.

The idea that the current educational trend is rather inclined towards creating digital generalists instead of specialists in one digital solution was reiterated in response to the question on the challenges associated with the current market of digital solutions. In addition to pull factors, there are also push factors leading to this trend, cost being one of them. As digital solutions are taken up and become industry standards, they become high-cost products and educational institutions must change again the digital solution they use in the educational activities. This change of providers of digital solutions is anticipated to keep going in the future, and as such, universities need to be able to go from one provider to the other. The DigiNEB collection of digital solutions was given as an example of an instrument that can be consulted in order to identify new products, especially Open Access products that can be adopted quickly in educational programmes. On the other side, a different view was expressed later on in the discussion, on the need to adapt the tools developed in the academic sector to the practice sector, as some of these tools are considered to require a high degree of knowledge to master them. The matter was further discussed when debating the appropriateness of the technology readiness levels in relation with the skills and knowledge of foreseen users. More consideration should be given to the users of the tools, as a perceived discrepancy is noted between the developers of the tools and the users. Developers might not have the professional field experience that end users have. With disruptive technologies becoming more the trend and the professional context evolving in terms of digitalisation levels and complexity of technology used, universities become test beds for or laboratories for real life implementation of digital solutions. Suitability of technology readiness levels of the products used when interacting with citizens was also addressed during the discussions. These solutions should be fit for purpose and in order to correctly and exhaustively identify these needs, a thorough analysis should be conducted.

Correctly embedding tools in practice is important, in order to make sure they fit their purpose. In addition to the point mentioned previously about contextualising the learning process of using a certain digital tool, a similar argument was made on the need to couple skill development with the stages of a certain project and the project brief: “having each of those constructively aligned to the project briefs. Making sure that they're using those tools at those specific points within the project, so they're actually relevant”.

The digital twin transformation, digital transformation and green transformation are mentioned as interconnected programmes facilitated by the European Commission. Digital twins and AI are mentioned as examples of the transformation taking place in the industry space, a trend that has an impact on educational requirements. The learning and educational needs are identified not only from the perspective of the educational institutions, but they also become evident in the

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workspace, as digitalisation pushes the need for reskilling and upskilling of the workforce. The digital transformation has led to the creation of new roles within companies, such as that of Chief Data Officers. Mentioning that many industry sectors are in the process of their digital transformation, a respondent added that: “The sustainability dimension is much more important because the impact is there for society; the digital transformation is required, but because the green transition will be possible only if it is enabled by technology, by the digital technologies”. Programmes of reskilling or upskilling, addressed to people who are already employed, are aimed at facilitating the acquisition of new digital skills. These digital literacy programmes have to be broad enough since they are not aimed at computer scientists, but narrow enough to develop the needed skills at the right level for being able to remain competitive in the respective sector.

■ 1.2.4 Digital solutions for facilitating engagement

While the NEB programme aims to have an overarching impact at the European level, national level characteristics and conditions require national adaptations. Policies addressing climate actions are bounded by geography, one representative case being the Netherlands, with its profile of a low-lying delta country. From this member state, a representative of the NEB programme at national level mentioned acting as a facilitator between the NEB, ministries and citizens in order to stimulate fit for purpose and long-term planning. In planning accordingly and for the longer term, citizens have been engaged in dialogue with policymakers, government representatives and spatial planning agencies in a “Ministry for the future” scenario and data collection activities via questionnaires and surveys. Engaging citizens should go beyond the stage of input collection and identification of needs and should become a multi focused exercise for collectively identifying solutions for long-term problems and raising awareness about the impact and consequences of alternative options. This can strengthen support for public policies and contribute to coherent implementation. The use of VR was not acknowledged as a solution for interacting with citizens in this purpose. However, the use of VR has been showcased in line with the NEB objectives in other activities of the DigiNEB project conducted in the same country. This discrepancy shows again the fragmentation across the landscape and, we might argue, the fact that visibility of certain initiatives is hindered by the combination of high volume and small scale of these initiatives.

Engaging with the broader audience (citizens, members of parliament etc.) by means of digital solutions is not only an input gathering exercise but can also be an alternative way of communication a certain message. Visual communication is an important function of digital tools. One specific benefit of using digital solutions is that of facilitating understanding by visualising a complex physical artefact, such as a building with historical buildings being particularly well suited for this approach. Historical buildings needing major investments in order to “receive a second life” are best understood by stripping down their layers and bringing them together in a visual whole showcasing a complexity that otherwise would remain opaque. Digital tools make different layers of the building visible, thus making complexity visible. In the case of often sophisticated historical buildings, the use of visualisation solutions and immersive environments such as BIM, contribute to resurfacing or regaining lost knowledge over historical methods of design and construction. This perspective received support from other participants in the discussion. For showing the combined impact of the building, including its performance to stakeholders, BIM can be used to visualise different elements of a building. During this exercise the challenge of interoperability of different digital solutions (such as PLM) used for the design of different objects or elements within the building surfaces.

On the question of suitable TRL levels of the existing digital solutions for citizen engagement, interventions in the focus group suggested that there is a mismatch in this area. Examples of citizen engagement initiatives included energy communities or neighbourhood level communities, for engagement and communication with which no suitable software was found that would

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not represent a barrier. Adapting types of digital solutions and TRL levels to age groups was discussed during the focus group, as participants mentioned the use of drones raising the interest of young adults (students). Low barrier technology such as the iPad can be used for wide engagement and is reported being used for this purpose in the “Minister of the Future” reported scenario. Participants also suggested that public institutions from different levels can develop and deploy different tools that can be used for interactions on different scales with the public in a simplified manner.

Google maps was given as example of general digital solution that can be used widely for interacting with citizens and the example determined positive reactions from many participants in the focus group. In addition to these general tools, professionals have at their disposal sophisticated tools for visualisation that require accounts, registration or even security clearances for using them in certain projects. What is lacking according to participants are digital solutions that offer the same functionalities but without the entry hurdles. An example from the Netherlands in this regard was that of the topographical time travel map where different past versions of a geographical space can be visualised. It was related that in a brainstorming discussion on using this digital solution, a minister for spatial planning expressed the interest of having a forecasting function of visualisation. Such functionality would be useful also when engaging with the broader public while debating long-term planning of public policies having a wide societal impact.

While scattered digital solutions are used, a missing solution is the one offering a centralised system for these tools. An example that is named in this sense is the Unreal Engine 5 for digital twins, appreciated because it can handle large data sets. A solution working towards building elements of a global digital twin is desired, that can facilitate visualisation of real time data able to “see construction level data [...] through levels of detail or load being able to see real time data [enabling] having a full master map of the entire planet, a full 3D model with all information on construction and materials and sustainability and energy have been able to map productively in the future.” In the participants’ view, such an exclusive online solution offering these functionalities would allow for wide engagement from members of the community, designers, engineers, etc. Of note is that when asked, participants acknowledged that having so much information available online does present potential risks. Curation of data becomes a challenge given the exponential increase of the available volume of data. As the sheer volume of data becomes overwhelming. A moderation process is needed in order to make data intelligible and meaningful. While acknowledging the risk of such a large volume of data falling into the wrong hands if making data public, the benefits of using digital solutions such as GIS or some form of mapping or 3D modelling on these data and being able to work with live data is invaluable.

An approach balancing the digital and the analogue is needed, for both security and inclusion purposes since this would “also mitigate the dangers of having [...] all [that information] out there and rather having it in a controlled digital protected environment that is then selectively presented to the public in person”. The idea of analogue alternatives is in alignment with opinions expressed during discussions on the use of AI, namely that while concentrating on digital tools, the focus on different ways of engaging with people should not be lost, since that is the ultimate goal: “Exclusions [of means of interaction] are not beneficial” and have been put in relation to the current state of affairs of undergoing a “digital transition”. Digitalisation should be a choice, an option for engagement, not an obligation. This opinion has received group support, with additional comments on the fact that while community engagement should be a choice, the professional public (architects, designers, planners) does not understand how to engage with the wider audience. It has also been noticed that digital tools are used for their nudging function of starting a conversation that afterwards is developed in its analogue alternative. The analogue and the digital should not be mutually exclusive but should complement each other: “There are good practices [...] that combine the [analogue with the digital] that use digital twins and AI simulations of different variants of

solving certain issues within cities as a basis of very analogue participation. [...] There are triggers of a certain change or enabled by the digital twin and by certain AI tools that are then publicly discussed and are brought into the conversation in a very analogue and very direct collaborative way”. Despite perceived delays, participants do believe that digital twins will become a reality.

External or push factors such as the COVID pandemic and the war in Ukraine contribute to driving innovation, as (sometimes niche) digital solutions need to be developed fast for problems that previously did not exist. Digital solutions developed for sustainability and economic growth can be deployed in unanticipated ways, such as using available digital solutions when the war in Ukraine broke out in order to map escape routes. In the participants’ view, the war in Ukraine has triggered a shift in priorities towards the defence sector and a raised awareness of additional vulnerabilities such as those arising from climate change.

The Green Deal and entrepreneurship are acknowledged as visible topics on the political agenda of the EU. A correlation has been observed by participants between the Horizon Europe programme and growing entrepreneurship initiatives. The programme therefore favours entrepreneurship to the development of digital solutions for the industry or direct employment in the private sector. The programme also shows potential for scaling up of these entrepreneurship activities, and a “big growth in the field of built environment [is seen] because so many informatics and engineers coming from other fields are getting into the built environment market”.

Fig. 11. Quotes DFG– focus on education and learning

■ 1.2.5 Miro Board inputs

Regarding the main platforms used for training, respondents mentioned that, to their knowledge, there is no platform that combines all product spheres and all user groups and no single tool that combines all needs. For facilitating public engagement, new kinds of digital interfaces are needed to enable participation without access to specialist and expensive tools. Combining digital tools with in-person engagement is necessary, as well as coupling digital participatory tools that are straightforward with direct conversation. Other suggestions included variable design cognition, in line with different ways of learning. Tools such as LinkedIn learning and Archistar are considered great repositories, but their outperforming of traditional teaching is questioned.

Fig 12 The main platforms used for training and developing of skills. DFG focus on education and training.

Questioned on the strengths and weaknesses of tools and projects focusing on training and skills, respondents mentioned that some digital tools require a large amount of specialist knowledge and therefore impractical for use by designers, engineers, and architects alike. In the design of tools it is essential that the end user is considered, such as the professional, the academic or members of the general public.

- In education it is important to provide a curriculum that enables students to understand the tools
- Depersonalisation is probably the biggest weakness of available tools, alongside difficulty in finding tailored platforms and required digital literacy. Cost and language barriers are another issue.

Strengths:

- always accessible
- always online
- removes barriers to education (e.g. can pay to access specific skills)

Weaknesses:

- can be expensive to access
- can require specialist hardware (leading to digital poverty)
- information may exclude certain demographics (e.g. not available in all languages).

Fig. 13. The strengths and weaknesses of tools and projects focusing on training and skills. DFG focus on education and training.

The digitalisation needs that should be prioritized are:

- Competence of evaluating the ecological impact of the use of digital tools
- Centralisation
- All software vendors are reactive to emerging technology rather than working towards a common unified tool
- (globally accessible digital twin with variable levels of detail)
- Tools that allow us to record the performance of a design over the life cycle of a building (design, use and deconstruction) and communicate it to key stakeholders.
- Accessibility:
- remove paywalls to key software, particularly to those in education.
- Tools that allow us to record the performance of a design over the life cycle of a building (design, use and deconstruction) and communicate it to key stakeholders.

Fig.14 Digitalisation needs that should be prioritized. DFG focus on education and training.

The respondents mentioned the following main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe:

- The growth of a circular and regenerative construction sector;
- The digital transformation;
- The green transition.

Fig. 15. Main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe. DFG focus on Education and training.

What does trustworthy AI mean to you?

21 responses

Fig. 17. What does trustworthy AI mean to you?

From participants perspective; attributes of trustworthy AI are:

- accountable;
- unbiased;
- accessible;
- accurate;
- aligned;
- benevolent;
- lawful;
- reliable;
- representative;
- reproducible;
- transparent;
- functional;
- fair;
- fit to the current problem.

Other mentioned elements of trustworthy AI are: ethics of the [system] provider [i.e. developer] and trusted data sources. The latter point connects to the “unbiased”; “representative” and, arguably, to the “fit to the current problem” requirements.

Respondents’ awareness of the state of affairs regarding issues around AI seems high. This conclusion can be drawn on the fact that the characteristics indicated can be grouped in different categories of issues spanning the spectrum of top priorities and challenges of the present-day agendas of AI developers and regulators:

- Traits of the how AI system function: possibility for user inquiry, including accessibility, ease of use – functionality,
- Traits of how AI system are deployed, relating to lawfulness and accountability.
- Traits relating to the fit between a certain system, the specific environment it is deployed in and the way it attains its goal.

Traits relating to lawfulness and accountability can be seen as risk mitigation measures on the part of the user, who can rely on *a priori* vetting of the law of the system they are interacting with.

Two outlier interventions mentioned trustworthy AI as being “utopia” and an “extension of me”. The fact that trustworthy AI was characterized as “utopia” indicates a pessimistic view and negative evaluation of the feasibility of AI being trustworthy, while alignment with the self implies a user-centric approach to validating the purposefulness of the AI system. This comes back to the user acceptance models. Transparency about the development phase, including what values were embedded in the model, and the deployment phase - how it is used - are necessary for user acceptance. Interestingly enough, trustworthiness was also mentioned as a risk in response to the question on main risks related to AI.

Based on which criteria do you choose a certain AI application?

Fig.18. Criteria for choosing a certain AI application

Criteria mentioned by participants for choosing an AI application are:

- price;
- accountability and auditability and explainability;
- contractual warranties;
- availability;
- ease of use, quality of results, fairness;
- fit for the [...] problem [it is meant to solve];
- repairable;
- availability of a free trial version;
- explainability, business model, and a two-way path to getting [...] data back in a usable way.
- Responsible design of tools [M].

These criteria can be grouped in financial, technical and value-oriented factors. Given the novelty of the technology and the fact that users can navigate through different alternatives in order to test them and identify best solutions in relation to a specific use, cost is a factor when choosing an AI application not only in absolute terms, but also in terms of the report between the added extra benefits of an alternative/ niche/ solution in relation to a general (and subscription-based) solution. This leads to the discussion of market shares of multipliers and the exponential growth of this share based on continuous improvement due to daily mass usage. If the current trend of big suppliers dominating the market continues, so too will the improvement of their products continue, and as such, they will most likely outgrow niche solution providers in terms of cost-functionality report. The European AI factories initiative should be noted in relation to this trend, as development of EU developed AI alternatives should be conducted in apparel with consumption of multiplier developed solutions in order to, if not close the technological gap, at least slow down its increase (Popa, 2024).

Both product liability and value alignment are referred to by users when choosing an AI system, with the latter including fairness. The fact that an AI system is also covered by product liability was touched upon the respondents, who mentioned contractual warranties; accountability and auditability and explainability as criteria used when choosing an AI system.

Suitability of the AI system for the specific problem it is meant to solve was mentioned several times by participants as a factor when choosing an AI application. This raises the issue of comparison between alternative solutions in terms not only of cost but also of functionality. Given the multitude of solutions, users have little to go on for choosing the right solution for a specific problem. Instruments for comparing functionalities of different AI solutions are welcome. In this regard, the DigiNEB project offers an overview of domain specific AI applications, tagging main functionalities and thus contributing to the ease of finding and choosing a solution for a specific problem.

The answer of “AI for AI vs AI for the problem” can be interpreted as prioritizing actual added value of using an AI solution versus its hype. Use of an AI solution should not only be about the hype, but should reflect an actual benefit, in terms of costs and time needed for the individual uptake of the technology versus the advantages the use of the solution itself brings to tackling a certain problem.

The contribution of “can it get me away from the 'blank slate' inertia when writing something to get ideas” can be interpreted in connection to the function the AI solution can have in relation to the extent of addressing the problem. The usage of an AI system does not have to be extended to solving the entire problem, or, put differently, it does not have to be exhaustive. It can also have a nudging function, aiding with the kick-start of a (creative) project or identifying the solution to a problem.

An additional function is that of amplification of abilities, therefore serving as enhancing mechanism, whether in terms of analysis capacity, pattern detection or speed of reaching a solution. Principles and the matter of imposition of “Big Tech” values are also mentioned when referring to the mechanism for choosing to use a certain digital solution or a certain provider: “we need to start with establishing our principles for the use of these tools and the impact on the stakeholders before we choose technologies or providers. We can't trust Big Tech to establish these for us. Each individual and company needs to have this before they start using AI tools”.

The main risks relating to AI are:

Fig.19. The main risks related to AI

- The main risks relating to AI as identified by participant are:
- Disinformation;
- Inaccurate data / AI trained in bias way / AI trained on other AI data;
- Reliability and critical reflection of the results;
- 'AI' itself; Bias; Clarity and lack of trust;
- Privacy and terms of use for the company using it;
- Model level security/safeguarding (racism, bias, ethical data collection/management);
- AI-enabled products or application-level safeguarding: User Experience;
- Trustworthiness;
- Job losses [for certain sectors such as the creative sectors];
- Loss of expertise with increase of undependable information.
- Total dependency of humanity [on] AI;
- A huge investment in intelligent machines rather than intelligent people;
- Enough knowledge and understanding [on the part of the AI system] of human diversity;
- Overuse, and disconnection between power and accountability;
- Invisible shifting of power from public to private realms;
- The prevalence of AI discourse in all domains, to the exclusion of other topics.

Most of the main risks relating to AI as identified by participants are a reflection of the effects of the technology within the broader ecosystem in which it is deployed, the technological dependencies, structural shifts of power and control, issues of bias and privacy, and job losses. Risks regarding the technical functioning of the AI systems have been mentioned, but to a lesser extent.

In addition to being part of the defining EU approach to AI systems, trustworthiness is also seen as a risk by respondents and this can be interpreted in different ways. (Over)reliance on technology can weaken human cognition and critical thinking and lead to technological scope creep. Connected to this is a potential growing power difference between technology developers, deployers and users. This then feeds into the discussion detailed above of AI in particular going against the general trend of technology democratising society.

Not being critical of the way technology functions, how it is developed and by whom and how it is deployed and not consciously curating alternatives as mitigation measures (for avoiding lock-ins for example) can lead to path dependencies and other broader technological, economic, social and political vulnerabilities. Constant critical debate between developers, deployers and users is needed in order to align expectations. The need for human inquiry as third line of defence in the case of high-risk systems is emphasized by the EU AI Act, which requires human oversight as part of deployer obligations. The positioning towards adopting AI systems could be mapped against a continuum, oscillating between trust, multidirectional debate (middle ground position) and rejection of technology. Trust towards the AI system can be determined/influenced by different factors (Popa, 2024), such as:

- unassuming reliance on technology as expressed values – preference towards bold technological development instead of cautionary regulation-driven development and uptake;
- previous positive interaction with technology;
- trust in the benevolence of the technology's deployer;
- low digital and AI literacy levels (lack of understanding of risks).

The dystopian perspectives are further strengthened by participant comments relating to the dangers of overreliance on AI. In an anticipated Orwellian perspective, uncritical and increased consumption of AI can lead to a balance shift between human and machine levels of cognition, and “total dependency of humanity [on] AI”. There is a wider debate to be conducted here. From a very practical perspective, cognition and critical thinking are needed in order to correctly interpret the output of an AI system, understand when the system is “hallucinating” or take the final decision on an outcome first facilitated by AI (oversight/ human in the loop function). From a wider perspective, experts consider that because AI generates outputs based on the data it was trained on, it is doomed to produce outputs in line with what it had previously learned (what it previously ingested): “AI is stuck reflecting what was seen in the past” (Vallor, 2024) and thus complete reliance on it will result in “Automating the ghost of the past into our future” (Vallor, 2024).

These feeds into the debate of what tasks should be taken over by AI and in what measure can the black box effect be overcome. Other experts criticise however this negative perspective of AI development, suggesting that those fearing loss of control and claiming an existential risk being associated with AI do not understand neither the technology nor the ecosystem needed to sustain it (Birhane, 2024). People's fears of AI come mostly from seeing it as fully autonomous, characteristic that is contested by some scholars.

A potential technological dependency can also have the effect of a structural shift in the power and control balance between developers, deployers and users. This concern is showcased in the participant observation that there can be an invisible shift of power from public to private realms, most likely as a reflection of the market shares of large private AI developers (multipliers)

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and the negotiation power (or lack thereof) between (even) large deployers such as government organisations and other public institutions. This power imbalance potentially also affects the way an AI system can comprehend and adequately represent the perspectives and, therefore, the interests of different and diverse user population, reflecting issues of bias, as developers determine training data selection, or values infused in the system. The danger of bias when it comes to the use of AI is widely acknowledged by practitioners, policymakers and researchers alike. Respondents mentioned in this regard factors such as: inaccurate data, bias, (AI trained in a bias way) and AI trained on other AI data; racism, ethical data collection/management.

Disinformation is one risk also addressed in the emerging scientific literature regarding the range of possibilities of AI solutions that can be used in both offensive and defensive purposes. Given the respondents group composition, disinformation is a risk acknowledged by the wide professional community, and (arguably) connected to the source of data used to train the models, the potential biases embedded in the system. An additional comment on the aspect of bias added in the Miro Board was “how does cultural or racial code-switching make it hard to collect data on intersectional or under-represented groups?”, reiterating thus the importance of data and model representativeness.

The deployment of rule-based AI systems affects repetitive tasks where human intervention becomes redundant due to the faster accomplishment of the task by/with the help of an AI solution/algorithm, leading to job loss or job reclassification. The effect is not only limited to the repetitive tasks, but also felt in the creative industries, where creative tasks are taken over by Generative AI: participants indicating job loss in the case of graphic designers and artists. With this job loss comes also the loss of expertise or internalised knowledge. As human unfiltered information spreads and exponentially grows throughout the ecosystem through repeated acts of consumption, future prevalent information might become unreliable, due to lack of human filtering. This might be interpreted as a prediction at this moment in time, but it reflects users’ perceptions and fears regarding possible technological development and should be addressed by both AI developers and policymakers. An additional qualitative negative shift in the job market was reflected by participants, together with absolute numbers of affected jobs comes, namely the loss of [human] expertise and increase of undependable information. All these negative evaluations should be taken with a grain of salt, as answers align with the initial request of identifying the risks of AI. The attention inflation that AI receives is also criticised by respondents, as it comes at the expense of other topics of interests. There is also the perception that the attention and resources invested in AI come at the expense of investments done in people. Additionally, expansion of “agenda time” dedicated to the topic might have exponential growth effects, exacerbating resource allocation discrepancies. This can also be related to the perspective indicated in the question on Human centric AI, discussed in the following section.

Last but not least, risk is also addressed by participants in relation to the balance between risk aversion and risk taking: “Aversion and risk-taking: Where are the areas [where] each [is] important?”. In a broader perspective, this can be interpreted in relation to the culture of the technology sector, namely more focused on free (up to the level of aggressive) technology innovation and therefore more risk-taking, as the US market is considered, or rather regulation focused – and thus risk-averse, as is the EU market.

Human centric AI is about:

Fig. 20 Human centric AI

- AI is a good servant but a poor master;
- “Form follows meaning”- the way we make sense of the AI is embedded in how we use it;
- Literacy;
- Technology traditionally democratized, currently we see de-democratization of AI
- The public, the community members, having agency. Where does the power lie?
- It lets focus people on the things they most enjoy;
- Starts from human centric design principles, not the technology. Not what AI does but who it does it for and whom it does it to.
- AI tries to please you;
- Treating humans as humans, and AI as AI.
- Reduction of skill / understanding of how to do the thing you are asking AI to do.

The EU value and human centric perspective on AI was explored in this question. The effect that technology has on social inequality is a matter of debate, influenced by initial technology savvy levels in a certain social segment, technological gaps and cost of technology uptake. Traditionally, digitalisation and technology led to higher democratization, enabling information access and free flows of information. Paradoxically perhaps, AI both widens inequality gaps and democratizes society. Civil society and researchers have argued that AI has led to a centralisation of power. One respondent’s perspective suggests that the case of AI is different: [If] “Technology traditionally democratized, currently we see de-democratization of AI”. Arguably this is not completely accurate. Technology does lead to democratization, but this usually happens in time, as technology cost decreases and uptake spreads. As we are still in the early phases of AI development, with understanding gaps (block box effects) and high prices, it does seem that the perspective of AI reinforcing elite interests is valid, either due to control over the technology in terms of affordability and comprehensibility (literacy hereof) or/end due to monopoly over technological development. In

the case of the latter, power or market share is centralized in the hands of a few big developers (Birhane, 2024). This consumption trend is backed by alignment of research on AI being conducted in partnership with “Big tech” as reported by Birhane (2024). This can have both positive and negative effects, as researchers get first hand access to technology developer’s insight, but it could also lead to questions regarding impartiality of research results, should such collaborations be conditioned by NDAs covering unfavourable results. Indicators substantiating this behaviour in the past are media reports according to which big tech companies recommend scientists to avoid putting companies in a negative light and require vetting prior to publication (Business Insider, 2020) and reports of big tech firing employees following disagreements about ethics (Alan Turing Institute, 2024).

Not addressing these potentially monopolistic trends with countermeasures can lead to growing monopoly and value imposition by (EU) external providers. The trend is being countered in an indirect manner by so-called EU protect and promote measures, with certification mechanisms acting as protection measures and internal investments as promote ones, just to name a few. The trend is thus countered by initiatives such as the EU AI factories and the AI literacy obligation coming into force in February 25 for deployers. The effectiveness of these measures will only be confirmed after a longer implementation period. Additional general purpose AI literacy training is already being developed, even if not labelled as such, and most likely the training and educational offers will only evolve with time. However, at this moment in time and in relation to the actual need, AI literacy training programs and resources are limited, as also indicated by additional input provided by respondents in the Miro board. One such input mentioned that “there are probably only 5 teachers qualified to talk about AI in Sweden”. The topic of AI literacy is further explored in the dedicated sections here below. The EU AI factories topic also relates to value alignment. There can be a value conflict lack of alignment between big tech providers and some of the deployers of their systems. The 2021 case when Google fired its ethical team raised such concerns in the mass media, as did a similar decision of Meta.

The power relation is also influenced by a combination of factors, including the way the technology was designed and the users’ agency in relation to it, and the users or affected person’s AI literacy levels. Additional input on the power aspect was included by participants in the Miro board, namely: “Controlling information flows means controlling people's agency and decisions - AI is being shaped as a source of information, the basis for which is poorly understood and controlled by the few” [M] suggesting that the use of AI will determine power shifts within society driven by control on information flows, influencing and directing capabilities of those controlling the source of information. The fact that AI becomes a source of information has been previously appreciated as a risk, due to the inherent learning patterns and potential for endlessly propagating errors of bias.

While human or value-centric AI reflects the EU approach of focusing on values, there is an acknowledged tendency to anthropomorphise AI, reflected by respondents in their comments, most obviously in their dystopic perspectives over an AI-driven future, but also criticized as such “Treating humans as humans and AI as AI”. These perceived faults can be attributed to the design phase of the technology as instrument to reach a personalized goal. As such, the focus should be, as pointed by a respondent “Not what AI does but who it does it for and who it does it to”. This is again connected to the current hype of AI, which is seen as a negative aspect if being deployed just due to its current attractiveness not its actual use for the problem at hand.

An input fallacy or data fallacy is also suggested by participants: “AI tries to please you”. This fallacy has been previously extensively analysed by researchers, policymakers and developers, and explained as the fact that the AI system learns based on the input it has been provided with, therefore propagating inherited biases or mistakes. This is substantiated by input provided for the next question, indicating that an adverse impact of AI on society is the fact that it “normalis[es] prejudice”.

Main adverse impacts of AI systems on society are:

Resource dominance	Massive increase in energy use that keeps us using more fossil fuels	"The information wars are about to get worse", Yuval Noah Harari	Propagation of malicious practices
anthropomorphising AI and ascribing human traits to machine learning and AI tools.	Its power of obfuscated normalisation	Loss of critical thinking capabilities	Normalising prejudice
Reliance on AI doing a 'thing' so reduction in understanding / ability of doing it and so reduction in innovation.	Collective and targeted influence	The dominance of US spelling in all written communication.	Less belief on human minds

Fig.21. Main adverse impacts of AI on society.

The main adverse impacts of AI systems on society as indicated by participants are:

- Resource dominance;
- "The information wars are about to get worse", Yuval Noah Harari;
- Anthropomorphising AI and ascribing human traits to machine learning and AI tools;
- Loss of critical thinking capabilities;
- Reliance on AI doing a 'thing'; reduction in understanding / ability of doing it and [thus] reduction in innovation;
- The dominance of US spelling in all written communication;
- Massive increase in energy use that keeps using more fossil fuels;
- Propagation of malicious practices;
- Its power of obfuscated normalisation;
- Normalising prejudice;
- Collective and targeted influence;
- Less belief [in the] human minds.

The power unbalance or concentration of power is again emphasized here as an adverse impact that AI has on society in the shape of resource dominance. This can be either a reflection of market share of hyperscalers, big developers imposing their own values or practices (mentioned [proxi] example being that of spelling), or reflection of access to the technology itself. Despite this, externalisation is also mentioned as a necessity, the lack hereof making certain business models not viable. This can be translated in maturity levels of existing (alternative) AI solutions, sector maturity, the effect of the

so called “protect” measures or lack thereof: “consider what 'business models' are actually not viable unless you externalise”.

Respondents also believe that reliance or overreliance on technology has a negative effect on human cognition, as it can lead to loss or weakening of human cognition (“loss of critical thinking capabilities”; “less belief on human minds”; “reliance on AI [leading to] reduction in [human] understanding/ ability of doing and so reducing innovation). It is of note the number of mentions relating to the effect of AI on the sharpness of human cognition and innovation capacity, again carrying a cautionary tale and aligning with a dystopian long-term perspective. The danger of bias is at least twofold: first if being embedded in the data used for training the AI then because as multiplier effect in the output, strengthened by the effect of overreliance on AI. Bias is again mentioned as example of an adverse impact that AI has on society, in the form of “normalizing prejudice”. Any bias embedded in the data would thus be reinforced by this trend of (perceived) decreased cognitive inquiry, as overreliance on AI would grow. Maintaining and training critical thinking capacity is especially important because epistemic inquiry remains in the exclusive realm of the human overseeing the system. Asked to produce an output, the AI will produce it (again mentioning here the observed fact that the system would rather give the wrong answer than no answer at all) and not question the relevance or desirability of the request.

Human cognition also acts as a filter or natural adjusting mechanism. Additional input provided by participants indicated that: “trust requires a negotiation, conversation or dialogue between the entities who want to trust each other. Automation or machine-to-machine comms can short-circuit this dialogue. Or bad actors can use a flood of data to obscure their machinations”.

Disinformation, as well as being mentioned as a risk is also perceived as an adverse impact of AI on society. Disinformation has been reported as the main concern relating to AI use by the population, for example in the Netherlands (Dutch Data Protection Authority, 2023). Disinformation campaigns can be undirected, and have a wide, general, collective audience or they can be targeted, as indicated by the respondents: “collective and targeted influence” and “the information wars are about to get worse”. This perception can also be attributed to the current geopolitical tensions brought forward in the cyberspace by the war in Ukraine and Russia’s aggressive disinformation campaigns, in particular active in big election years such as 2024. A further investigation into who these (high value) (real or perceived) targets are would be beneficial. The participant contribution of “propagation of malicious practices” is a manifestation of disinformation campaigns. An additional mitigation or counter-measure for disinformation being mentioned is “due diligence on social media selection”.

Energy consumption is mentioned by participants as an adverse impact that AI has on society. Energy consumption of AI systems is a concern that is raised most often by researchers, policymakers and higher level stakeholders in the AI ecosystem. The fact that users are also aware of this indicates a high visibility of the topic within the professional user’s segment. The environmental footprint of AI is also to be considered when developing national or regional AI alternative initiatives, such as the European AI factories (Popa, 2024 forthcoming). While high energy consumption of AI systems is acknowledged by participants, the opposite overall effect is also acknowledged: sustainability and environmental protection are mentioned as examples of the positive impact that digital tools (including AI) can have. Participants are also aware that sustainability and environmental performance are key for the Bauhaus project, with AI being positively associated with environmental protection. Mass media reports (the Guardian, 2024) on the environmental impact of AI were also referenced by participants.

The paramount factor when choosing to deploy an AI application should be:

16 responses

Fig.22. The paramount factor when choosing to deploy AI

The conscious choice between different AI solutions was meant to test if uptake is driven by certain factors. The paramount criteria for choosing to deploy an AI application, according to participants, should be:

- accountability;
- alignment;
- applicability;
- clear stakeholder value;
- control reputational risk;
- how [AI] has been trained;
- human alignment;
- human supervision;
- interrogating aesthetics;
- [weather] AI is actually needed;
- monitoring tools;
- real optimisation gains;
- reliable and responsible;
- security by design;
- understand how it works;
- well defined problem.

These inputs can be clustered in three categories: value focused (accountability, stakeholder value, human alignment; interrogating aesthetics), security robustness in technical terms (human supervision; security by design) as well as in the systems’ effects (control reputational risks), and purpose alignment (stakeholder value; [actual need]; real optimization gains; well defined problem). The aesthetics of AI is perhaps a less often mentioned criteria for choosing an AI application, but it is fitting the needs and values of the creative industry. The fact that values received such increased attention in the respondents’ answers demonstrates the importance that values have in

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the EU approach towards technological development and practices towards technological deployment, but it can also be a reflection of globally shared perceptions and current concerns of AI technology development and deployment. This input preceded in a natural way the last question inquiring about the meaning of the European approach to Artificial Intelligence.

The European approach to Artificial Intelligence means:

Fig 23. The European approach to AI

The last question of the interactive session organised as “provocation” reflects the European AI focus around values. Being shaped as a provocation, the title of the exercise “tug of war – privacy versus security” was meant to challenge participants to prioritize values and reflect on the (perceived) distinctive character of what official policy documents call “the European approach to artificial intelligence”. Here, respondents’ answers were more complex in length and fewer in input, reflecting the complexity (and perhaps less known character) of the question.

Answers here included:

- In practise, enlightenment thinking and regulatory mitigations (avoiding impact to the military-industrial complex and border regime). Ideally, encouraging multiplicities and openness.
- A lot of good intentions, a top-down approach that should be culturally disseminated as bottom-up or citizen movement.
- Regulating something that is not properly understood.
- Protection of democracy. [With] 70 nations, accounting for around half the world’s population, heading to the polls this year, questions of truth and disinformation are top [concern].
- Creating AI safeguarding principles in the same way we created Privacy By Design principles;
- Will the risk-based AI Act become a global standard as GDPR has become? Don't believe that tech companies will have the best human interest in mind. Their interest is solely [monetary].
- Being able to set standards especially around curation.

The need for enlightenment thinking reflects the amplitude of the elements that need to be taken into consideration when developing, deploying and regulating such a complex technology in a manner adapted to the specifics of a given context, i.e. the European one. Redundancy and openness are encouraged, as is alignment with democratic values and practices. The critical approaches to the question of the European approach to AI seem to indicate that current top-down approaches are good intended but lack in outreach, since bottom-up citizen dissemination is called for. This is not necessarily a request for a change of approach but rather a call for additional complementary action for broader impact. Additionally, a criticism of the EU approach to focusing on regulation is found in one of the provided answers, suggesting a dissonance between levels of understanding of the technology and levels of complexity of the legislation regulating that certain technology: “regulating something that is not properly understood”. Previous research has shown that legislation is running behind technology development as the effect of the difference in speeds between the technological and legislative fields. The input provided here suggests this distance is not only exacerbated but also perhaps skewed by the fact that lack of correct understanding might lead to gaps or errors in the regulatory frameworks. It should be noted therefore that periodic reviews and additions of the regulatory frameworks are advised, as was the case of the GDPR being complemented by case law interpretation of the courts. Reflection of EU’s focus on regulation is the emphasis on safety standards and safeguarding principles in a similar fashion to privacy by design principles. A potential clash of values between European regulators focusing on developing and imposing risk-based standards and big tech developers, rather than focused on financial gain, is suggested by the respondents.

The high-risk cases of AI deployment are also acknowledged (border control, military use) both as reality and implicit as areas where over-regulation should be avoided. Regulation also serves a mitigation purpose, and acts as demarcation between mainstream (civilian) use of AI and exempted use, namely military and law enforcement/ border control use. Again, interventions demonstrate general awareness regarding mainstream legislation and exemptions hereof and (most likely) the contested debates around military, law enforcement or surveillance use of AI.

Fig.24. Interactive output collection on the Challenge on values and security for AI

■ 1.3.2 AI workshop part 2 - Deconstructing AI literacy

The “Deconstructing AI Literacy” workshop was a 2-hour – two-part hybrid session. The design of the interactive board for the workshop “Deconstructing AI Literacy” is found in the Annex section. The

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official participant list included over 30 registrations for either online or offline participation. Online participation rates were under the anticipated official registration rates (something that is not unique to such activities).

The subject was introduced via a live presentation and discussion on the formal requirements of the AI Act regarding literacy levels of AI system developers and deployers, the legal requirement which will come into force in February of 2025. After the presentation, onsite and online participants were presented with the different organisational roles that interact at one point or another of the AI system lifecycle with the product, with the AI product lifecycle stages, or with the expected learning outcomes of a possible AI training programme.

Fig.25. Introductory presentation in the Deconstructing AI literacy workshop.

The initial presentation was meant to stimulate a discussion about levels of literacy depending on roles and responsibilities. The interactive presentation on Deconstructing AI Literacy addressed the following topics:

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Recital 20 AI Act

In order to obtain the greatest benefits from AI systems while protecting fundamental rights, health and safety and to enable democratic control, AI literacy should equip:

- providers,
- deployers and
- affected persons

with the necessary notions to make informed decisions regarding AI systems.

Recital 20 AI Act

Those notions may vary with regard to the relevant context and can include understanding the:

- correct application of technical elements during the AI system’s development phase,
- the measures to be applied during its use,
- the suitable ways in which to interpret the AI system’s output,
- in the case of affected persons: the knowledge necessary to understand how decisions taken with the assistance of AI will have an impact on them.

AI LITERACY (AI ACT)

‘AI literacy’ means:

- skills,
- knowledge
- understanding

that allow

- providers,
- deployers
- and affected persons,

[...] to make an informed deployment of AI systems, as well as to gain awareness about the opportunities and risks of AI and possible harm it can cause.

IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE

- From February 2025, organisations that use AI systems must also have sufficient knowledge about AI.
- The level of AI literacy of each employee must be in line with the context in which the AI systems are used and how (groups of) people may be affected by the systems.
- Developers should include in the documentation package the appropriate AI literacy levels for the deployers, in line with the desired purpose.

Appropriate AI literacy of deployers and users

Rule based AI		Machine Learning			Generative AI		
Not-Impactful	Impactful	Not-Impactful	Impactful	High-risk AI	Not-Impactful	Impactful	High Risk AI
-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X

Stages in the AI lifecycle

Fig.27. Content from the introductory presentation in the Deconstructing AI literacy workshop.

[Definition of] AI literacy

AI literacy = “an individual's ability to clearly explain how AI technologies work and impact society, as well as to use them in an ethical and responsible manner and to effectively communicate and collaborate with them in any setting. It focuses on knowing (i.e. knowledge and skills).”.

AI competency = “an individual's confidence and ability to clearly explain how AI technologies work and impact society, as well as to use them in an ethical and responsible manner and to effectively communicate and collaborate with them in any setting. They should have the confidence and ability to self-reflect on their AI understanding for further learning. It focuses on how well individuals use AI in beneficial ways.”(Chiu, 2024).

Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes of AI literacy trainings have to combine:

- Technological elements,
- Legal and ethical elements,
- Sector specific knowledge.

Topics:

- Foundations of AI [technical]
- Technical aspects and safety
- Data
- Bias and non- discrimination
- Legislation relating to AI
- Governance of AI
- Fundamental rights
- Privacy and data protection
- Contract management
- Sustainability

Roles:

- DEVELOPER
- DEPLOYER
- AFFECTED PERSON (CITIZENS)

Other roles interacting with the AI:

- Contract manager
- Policy specialist
- Archive specialist
- Data engineer
- Data Scientist
- Security Officer
- Project leader
- Process owner
- Privacy Officer
- Information analyst
- Security Officer

The interactive exercise asked participants to structure and evaluate AI literacy skills for 3 different roles: developer, deployer and impacted person (citizen). In the context of the exercise, the three categories followed the role conceptualisation found in the AI Act, namely that of developer, deployer, and the natural person affected by the AI system was defined as “citizen (affected person)”. Respondents were also asked to indicate examples for each role, in order to better contextualize answers. As such, developers’ roles were associated with machine learning activities and examples of deployers included providers such as OpenAI and Fal.ai. This “confrontation” on literacy levels had at least a two-fold purpose: to challenge participants in reflecting upon and (eventually) acknowledging different needs in the AI literacy levels of the different roles in the ecosystem and to evaluate the literacy differences among the roles. The design of the exercise included in addition to the evaluation of overall and specific AI literacy elements also appreciations on the understanding of societal good and societal harm in the case of AI systems. The formulation of the question left enough space for interpretation in order to capture a broad palette of perspectives.

Of the three roles, the most challenging to complete proved to be the profile of the citizen/affected person since it is a broad category that can interact in different degrees with the AI system or only be affected by it. The question therefore goes into the broader discussion of what should be appropriate levels of AI literacy in a democratic society. The initial design of the activity involved evaluation on a five-point Likert scale the different literacy levels required of the three roles, in order to better calibrate training literacy programmes. The premise of the task was that different roles that interact with the AI will require different levels. For example, in addition to technical skills and knowledge developers also need to be aware of how potential for bias and discrimination being built in the system and also of AI legislation. While it can be argued that in the case of the affected person (citizen), there is no legal requirement for AI literacy, this is needed in order for the citizen to be aware of how they are being impacted by AI systems in their daily lives and how they can best protect their rights in relation to developers and deployers.²

After the evaluation of the literacy needs, participants were asked to indicate what are the dangers of low AI literacy levels for each role. In the case of the affected person (citizen) responses confirm the above mentioned hypothesis, namely that low AI literacy has an impact of the exercising of rights.

² The task of evaluating the levels of literacy on a point 5 likert scale (see Figure 28 here below for details) was the least addressed of all, and as such will not be reported upon.

DEVELOPER

Your Role/Organisation sector

Dangers of low AI literacy

Type something

Main literacy content:

Knowledge about

Type something

Skills

Type something

Understanding of:

Type something

Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI

Type something

Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI.

Type something

Knowledge of risks of AI development

Type something

Literacy Level
Rate the required literacy level

Governance of AI

Fundamental rights

Privacy and data protection

Contract management

Sustainability

Literacy Level
Rate the required literacy level

Foundations of AI [technical]

Technical aspects and safety

Data

Bias and non-discrimination

Legislation relating to AI

Fig.28 Detailed view on the evaluation form of AI literacy needs for the developer role.

Fig. 29. Comparative AI literacy needs evaluation for 3 roles: developer; deployer and affected person/ citizen

Table 1. Main dangers of low AI literacy for different roles interacting with AI

Developer	Deployer	Citizen (Affected person)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSFW systems; High technical costs; Lack of data for certain use cases; Performance implications; Bias; Misunderstanding the Technology's limitations; Compliance with regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Failed Product; Violation of GDPR and AI Act; Spread of misinformation; Misinformation and Misuse; Privacy and Security Risks; Ethical Concerns and Accountability; Instability and low robustness; Lack of transparency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cannot compete. Less learning potential; Being scammed, fraud, susceptible to misinformation; Over-reliance on AI; Misunderstanding the Technology's Limitations.

One of the dangers of low AI literacy in the case of citizens is the fact that they cannot compete. This can refer to either the use of AI systems while performing work related tasks, thus the use of technology in professional contexts, the understanding of how AI development trends might impact workforce dynamics or how AI systems impact chances of employment, when used, for example during recruitment screening processes. Lack of possibility to compete because of low literacy level is connected to a lower learning potential, and can be both a cause and an effect of this.

AI literacy for developers

As developers are responsible for the way technology is developed, most answers given by participants regarding what deployers should know about AI as part of AI literacy packages include technical elements, namely: GPU and energy use; hallucination detection; dilution aspects; developing AI models, processing demands, development methodology, programming languages, machine learning operations and deep learning algorithms, fine-tuning of models; LORA's, system constraints and development skills for the proper development environment. Developers should also have an "understanding of how to read and analyse existing research papers and implement them". This suggests that the research world has valuable (different) insight that developers should take into account or benefit from. Developers should also be aware of implementation frameworks,

legislation, ethical aspects, user requirements. etc. These requirements are perhaps difficult to achieve for developers addressing a global market, since resources would need to be scaled up to these broad markets. Additionally, aspects such as ethics and user requirements might require market-to-market adaptation, something that might fundamentally change the functioning of the AI system, which could not be in line with the capability or willingness of the deployers. Not embedding this adaptability in turn and going for a standard product would mean possible misalignment between technology on the one side, users and context on the other. Additionally, in theory, this capacity for adaptability could be feasible for big tech representatives and less so for middle sector or small, niche developers.

Given the high energy usage that generative AI systems have, the fact that developers should have knowledge of GPU and energy use seems self-explanatory. The active effort of bringing down energy use is what should be required from developers. Developers can embed these sets of knowledge and skills in model cards facilitating transparency and correct deployment of the AI systems. For developers, knowledge of AI for societal good includes the possibilities of industries to use AI for growth or increase revenue. Arguably this is a direct positive impact on their own activity. In the case of industries oriented towards public service then this impact would indeed expand into the broader fabric or society. Knowledge of AI for societal harm includes how systems can be jailbroken and manipulated, how biased data affects results; algorithmic bias. The first line of defence in front of bias are the developers. In the case of big tech, these are both developers and deployers, and as such, they also bear the responsibility of fighting deepfakes and misinformation, monitoring and cleaning content. Developers should also have knowledge about the technology wars as part of greater knowledge on AI for societal harm. This can be analysed in different ways, first of all, as part of a market competition, not only as part of liberal democratic markets but also as part of global markets with players having antagonistic interests, developers must have an understanding of others behaviour and possible subversive actions. This is not only reflected in the possibility of losing market share, but also in the aggressive cyber-postures of opponents and, in the case of interdependent supply chains, in the risks of backdoor attacks, just to name a few. In order to be able to counter threats both for themselves and the deployers and final users, developers must be well aware of them and know what the weaknesses of the technology are. Knowledge of the risk of AI development includes how to gracefully handle misinformation and biases; how to set up systems to monitor outputs; what are societal bias in outputs and use of KPIs to detect anomalies;

Knowledge about:

- Gpu and energy use.
- Hallucination detection.
- Dilution aspects.
- Developing AI models.
- Processing demands.
- Development methodology. Programming languages etc.

Skills:

- Machine Learning operations
- Fine-tune of models
- LÖRA's
- Machine Learning and Deep learning algorithms.
- Development skills for the proper development environment

Understanding of:

- How to read and analyse existing research papers and implement them
- Implementation frameworks, system constraints.

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- Legislation, ethical aspects, user requirements. etc.

Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI include:

- How industries might use your system to benefit their growth or increase revenue.

Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI:

- How systems can be jailbroken;
- How systems can be manipulated in;
- Technology wars;
- How biased data affect results;
- Algorithmic Bias;
- Deepfakes and Misinformation;

Knowledge of risks of AI development:

- How systems can be jailbroken;
- How to gracefully handle misinformation and biases;
- How to set up systems to monitor outputs;
- Societal bias in outputs;
- Use of KPIs to detect anomalies;
- [are] Important.

AI literacy for deployers

Deployers have a vital role in the AI interacting ecosystem and they stand between developers and users, when they are not the developers themselves. They have numerous responsibilities according to the AI Act, and as such they need to have a high AI literacy level. AI literacy includes knowledge of the technical aspects of the technology, of its way of functioning, its limitations and weaknesses, the legislation that regulates it and additional pieces of legislation, ethical principles applicable in a certain context, user requirements, the functionality of the market and national, regional and global ecosystem. Similar to the knowledge that is expected from developers, deployers also need to have knowledge on how systems scale; how to maximize GPU usage; how to measure performance; ongoing system maintenance and updates, System performance in real-world scenarios.

Similar to developers, deployers need to have an understanding of Sectors and how they [work]; of the legislation and also need to be able to explain deployment of a system, choices made when doing so, risks and mitigation measures. In addition to the knowledge that is required from developers, deployers also need to know how to protect customer data and how to implement governance frameworks demonstrating responsible AI governance. Skills required from deployers include semantic analysis, machine learning and deep learning models, LLM. As products deployed on the internal market, AI systems are also covered by product safety legislation and by sector legislation.

On the part of deployers, understanding of AI for societal harm includes knowledge on how bad actors can inflict harm; knowledge on [how] manipulation and dissemination of false, harmful content function and the effects of incorrect citizen data (such as credit score, health, identification, etc). For deployers, risks of AI development include the lack of a specific problem for which an AI solution can be deployed, transparency or lack thereof, and flooding the internet with bad quality products.

Knowledge about:

- How systems scale.
- How to maximize GPU usage.

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- How to protect customer data.
- How to measure performance.
- Governance, test, Ongoing system maintenance and updates, System performance in real-world scenarios.

Skills:

- Semantic analysis
- Machine learning and Deep learning models, LLM

Understanding of:

- Sectors and how they [work]
- Legislation, explainability

Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI:

- Efficiency, accessibility

Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI:

- Efficiency, accessibility.
- Equipping bad actors to inflict harm.
- Manipulation and dissemination of false, harmful, or few content.
- Unwarranted.
- Incorrect citizen data (credit score, health, identification, etc)

Knowledge of risks of AI development:

- No clear problem to be solved.
- Turning the internet into a dumpster.
- Intensive knowledge.
- Transparency.

AI literacy for citizens/ the affected person

AI has a wide impact, being deployed in ways that are either visible or invisible for the end user/ citizen. Citizens can either choose to interact with an AI system, becoming users, or can be affected by processes based on AI systems, such as credit scoring, or AI present in the public space for security and surveillance purposes. For the affected person/citizen, understanding of the working of the AI tool or system includes its applications in terms of the practical benefits it can bring, such as upskilling and better career prospects. But AI use can also have negative impact of individuals' careers, not only positive ones, when, for example it is used for automated screening of CVs and candidate selection. Understanding of how such systems work on the affected persons side would first need transparency from the deployers side and afterwards training on the citizens side on how to adapt content to such filters.

For the citizen, or the affected person/ user, most knowledge elements mentioned by participants in the Digital Focus Groups refer to the awareness of the risks that the technology brings. The end user can be a conscious consumer of AI, deploying it for own purposes, or in a broader context, affected by processes or decisions facilitated by AI deployed by private companies or public institutions. AI facilitated decision making process affect the citizen even if not they are aware of it. In all scenarios, what the affected person should be aware of is the technology's weaknesses and limitations. Knowledge on how the technology functions also allows for "challenging" its results. Therefore, when designing AI literacy programs, attention must be paid not only to knowledge and skills for actively using AI but also to the limitations of its applicability in individual usage, and (perhaps more

relevant) in the case of systems used for by public organisations having a high impact either in terms of spread or consequences. In the latter case, awareness allows the affected person to react in line with the principle of protecting their own rights both in front of public authorities and against automated decision making in public or private entity facilitated processes. This is complemented by the need of knowledge and understanding of the legislation, as indicated by participants. Knowledge of the legislation can reflect the legislation on the topic of AI as technology, but also of connecting pieces of legislation, such as privacy or copyright law, and broader frameworks of civil rights and liberties.

Developers and experts have shown that an AI system is much rather inclined to give a false answer than to give no answer at all (Vallor, 2024), leading to the risk of so called “hallucination”. While some of these hallucinations are eye catching, others are less so, and as such, more difficult prevent from spreading as facts. Therefore, human inquiry is relevant especially in the latter cases, where human intelligence is needed to differentiate between what is conceptually of practically not possible, something that the AI system might not (yet) be able to perceive. Maintaining and developing critical thinking when using AI is important for overcoming these risks and the risk of weakened human cognition in time.

Critical thinking is mentioned both as knowledge and skills requirements for the affected person/citizen. Critical thinking can be put in the broader context of technological and digital literacy, which has a direct relationship with AI literacy. However, in the case of AI, the so-called black box effect still characterizes the functioning of the technology, for all groups interacting with it. Technology and digital literacy cannot account for AI literacy. Constant enquiry into how a certain AI system functions and how to interpret the results obtained allows for course corrections. Critical inquiry avoids overreliance on technology, that can affect the sharpness of human critical thinking and lead to the fallacy of repeating the past, as mentioned above.

This can also be connected to understanding of biases, another aspect mentioned by participants as part of what citizens need to have an understanding of. Critical inquiry contributes to allowing for interpretations and corrections, countering (to a certain extent) the risk of any error imbedded in the initial datasets spreading exponentially and countering the perverse effect of the AI model being trained on its own data going mad. Arguably, biases should first be recognised as being part of the initial datasets in order for their effects to be corrected. However, just general overall awareness of the existence and effects of biases can have a positive impact in relation to overall AI consumption effects, as precaution measure. The “human in the loop” or “over the loop” approach, understood here not as human oversight of high-risk AI processes in the sense of the AI Act but rather as individual interrogation of the AI systems way of functioning and of producing results is therefore needed for corrections and correct interpretations.

According to participants, not only independent usage of AI is important but also the ability to integrate AI in conventional approaches. This integration however is contested by different deployers regarding its appropriateness for risk management. In a setting outside the context of the Digital technical focus groups, AI experts expressed the concern that such integration of processes might actually increase the risks incurred by AI deployment, as damages can spread broader and have a higher impact when processes are complex whereas in simple processes, any potential damages are contained to that specific process. This is an interesting perspective that should be further investigated.

Therefore, for the user it is important to be aware of the limitations of technology, so that they can know in what measure can they rely on a certain AI facilitated result and how to interpret such results. Understanding of the technology itself is therefore relevant, not only relying on the benefits it brings in terms of quick results. This can be related to the speed versus loss of accuracy relation, which can be different depending on the context in which the system is used. If in some contexts,

high speed is preferred over higher accuracy, in others high accuracy is paramount. Understanding how the technology functions or foundational knowledge should be complemented by discipline area knowledge, again a factor that contextualises results of AI systems. This tacit knowledge than is what can counter the possible effects of AI “hallucinating”. An understanding of the effects and risks of using or embedding filtered materials or censorship is also mentioned by participants, again related to the risk of biased or skewed effects. Additionally, the affected person should also have knowledge about privacy and security risks and an understanding of ethics. On the point of ethics again, this can be interpreted in different ways: the ethical principles embedded within the technology, the ethical deployment of the technology, the ethical interpretation of its results, and, not in the least, the overall effect resulting from the intersection of all these aspects, meaning the ethics of a certain deployment of a certain technology, developed in a certain way, for a specific purpose and in a specific context.

AI for societal good is a broad concept, mentioned in the EU legislation but most likely differently defined and understood by different target groups. As such, the different points mentioned in parallel for the three roles give an overview of what is expected as action enabling societal good. In the case of the citizen, respondents mentioned understanding of multiplier effects theories, lowering of friction and interface training. Understanding multiplier effect would need specific addressing in AI literacy programs. Respondents also mention the positive effects that AI deployment can have, as effect of speeded processes or results – “efficiency” and “improved work-life-balance”. Societal good effects included also increased economic power, again related to improved career prospects.

On the point of societal harm, answers mentioned again multiplier effects, similar to the intervention on AI for societal good. This suggests that the AI itself does not bring positive or negative effects on its own, but rather that whatever the initial external purpose, its effects are exacerbated by the deployment of AI, either in a positive or a negative way. This underlines the fact that how technology is used determines its effects. Such being the case, it is that more important that the deployers of technologies are well aware of the implications and effects of their choices. Contrarily, technology development studies have shown that technology in itself is not neutral, but embeds certain values of the developer or the historical context in which it was developed. For example, the DARPA developed model of the Internet was characterized by network redundancy in order to be “bomb proof”, a technological requirement characteristic of technology being developed in the cold war era. Other examples of AI for societal harm include the risks streaming from easy dissemination of negative effects feelings of anger, harm violence, or defamation. Here again, whatever the purpose and effect of the context in which technology is deployed, the use of AI only exacerbates those initial uses and effects.

For the citizens, knowledge of the risks of AI development include the relation between the societal impact and the defined risk outputs. Given the complexity of both the technology and the legislation regulating it, awareness of the correct terminology is important also for the citizen, for example in order to know in front of whom they can make certain claims and claim certain rights. Additionally, on this topic, answers included knowledge on the vulnerability of companies (“how they can be manipulated”). This can be related to the topic of supply chain security or dependency, or the negotiating power that deployers have in front of developers. This power balance or lack thereof is a matter of debate, even in the case of governments when having to negotiate with big platform developers, or so-called multipliers.

Cost is another aspect mentioned in relation to risk of AI development, as it could have an impact on the choice of a certain solution or in time lead to lock-ins if, for example, transferring to a different provider would high require opportunity or transactional costs.

Knowledge about:

- Knowing the weaknesses of the technologies and their uses.
- Ability to integrate AI and "conventional" approaches
- Understanding of implications and limits
- How the tech works, and what is possible. How to critical think.
- Knowing the weaknesses of the technologies and their uses.
- Ability to integrate AI and "conventional" approaches.
- Understanding of implications and limits.
- Privacy and security risks.

Skills:

- Foundational knowledge in the discipline, critical thinking, common sense.
- Critical Thinking, Reasoning, General Computer Literacy.
- Foundational knowledge in the discipline, critical thinking, common sense
- Knowledge to evaluate and challenge.
- Critical thinking

Understanding of:

- Discipline area, risks stemming from heavily filtered materials, censorship.
- Biases.
- How the tools work, how they can upskill you, or improve your career prospects.
- Discipline area, risks stemming from heavily filtered materials, censorship. Biases.
- Legislation
- Ethical aspects.

Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI:

- Understanding of multiplier effects theories, lowering of friction, interface training.
- Can improve work/live balance, increased economic power and efficiency.
- Understanding of multiplier effects theories, lowering of friction, interface training.

Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI:

- Mandatory - multiplier effect once again.
- Anger, harm violence, defamation
- Mandatory - multiplier effect once again.

Knowledge of risks of AI development:

- Societal impact vs defined risk outputs. Language is important, proper wording mandatory (legal).
- How companies can be manipulated, costs of services, how to critical thinking.

AI perception and AI consumption trends

As both AI applications development and initiatives to regulate them take off, there is a media, policy and consumption inflation of AI systems. Some have called this the Wild West of AI, others call it a "hype", characterizations with a somewhat pejorative connotation. An inflated consumption while there is no comprehensive legislative framework in place can lead to errors, post factum evaluated as such. In the same time, legislation cannot be *a priori* comprehensive, given unanticipated results technology deployment has in specific contexts. It seems thus that at this moment in time these high levels of consumption cannot be avoided, as the interaction and influencing process of technology consumption and technology regulation has to be a natural one.

Users of AI systems report experiencing such a “hype”, deducing thus a personal or witnessed consumption that did not have the expected benefits. Users indicated “the prevalence of AI discourse in all domains, to the exclusion of other topics” as a risk associated with AI.

The report between actual added value of using an AI solution versus time needed to uptake the technology and resources needed for acquiring might not always be a positive one. The answer of “AI for AI vs AI for the problem” can be interpreted as prioritizing actual added value of using an AI solution versus its hype.

The patterns indicated in the technical working groups are consistent with results of other public consultations on risks and trust levels relating to AI systems. For example, in the Alan Turing lecture on Trust and AI (Birhane, 2024), when asked to name causes of worry when it comes to AI technologies, the respondents indicated privacy, ethics, misinformation, disinformation/bad actors, transparency, discrimination, bias, loss of control, loss of creativity, climate impact, security, sustainability, terrorism, deskilling, deepening/wealth inequality, manipulation, lack of regulation, surveillance, job losses etc. In a similar vein to the negative appreciation of the time dedicated to AI in the DigiNEB technical working groups, of note is a similar comment: “too much time wasted on AI” indicated conflicting priorities. On the point of manipulation and disinformation, all three investigated roles have a say in countering this danger, in different capacities and at different stages of the information manipulation or disinformation process.

Complex integration of AI facilitated processes might bring additional risks, as complex processes have complex multiplying and unforeseen effects. Overreliance on technology that can affect the sharpness of human critical thinking. Constant enquiry into how a certain AI system functions and how to interpret the results obtained by it allows for course corrections and correct interpretations. As technology is seen to enhance human capabilities, paradoxically it can simultaneously decrease them, as is the example of overreliance of AI having the potential risk of decreasing human cognition.

In the context of education activities and the education sector, AI is also used more and more often. AI literacy programs should include knowledge and skills for actively using AI and for actively understanding and proactively responding to its limitations during both individual usage and public or commercial deployments. Knowledge about the main and connecting legislations also enables citizens to better protect their rights.

Regarding the need to embed elements of technology limitations in AI literacy programs, experts and practitioners also discuss over AI failure workshops, which give practical insight into how and why AI systems fail. Arguably such workshops would give more in depth and lasting understanding of the current limitations of the technology. Identifying and mapping AI literacy components and levels proves of value for deployers with whom the legal obligation of AI literacy rests, who subsequently can set up training and awareness programmes for their specific purposes. As AI literacy rests on previous technological and digital literacy, an exhaustive mapping exercise of AI literacy requirements will result in a complex set of skills and knowledge, across a diverse variety of connected topics. Transposing this exhaustive mapping exercise in internal policies for training, skills and knowledge development and testing also for their internalisation or acquisition can transform in a top-down pressure for literacy acquisition. What comes across from the research focusing on AI is that some challenges are common across the landscape for those engaging with the technology, the users, while others are matters of priority or so called “luxury problems” – for the developers and the deployers. Examples of the latter being the complexity of governance models.

■ 1.4.1 Levels of digitalisation

Consistent with results from the other focus groups and desk research activities, participants indicated that digitalisation levels are different at country level but also present sector similarities or different particularities. Rather than the lack of a digital solution or low digitalisation being a problem, it was the multiplicity and overlap of digital solutions that was perceived as a challenge during this focus group, with the multiplicity and overlap of tools being seen as a hinderance. The question on the existing gaps in available digital solutions received answers in this sense. As such, this section presents the issue of current challenges of digitalisation not in relation to existing gaps but to the overwhelming volume of alternatives and lack of quality filters for differentiation. This final aspect - a quality filter for selecting between available tools – is indeed what is missing in the current landscape and is discussed in relation to the evaluation of the DigiNEB collection, in the Gap analysis section.

Discussing about tech solutions in general is perceived as not helpful or as deceiving because technology could be a solution in one area but not in another area. Contextualisation and customization of the analysis and the debate are needed.

Expressing views from the academic sector from two member states – Spain and France, one respondent mentioned that the level of digitalisation is low, taking into account BIM implementation and other software that are available in education programmes. In the construction sector, the respondent working in both France and Spain in the public and private sectors expressed the view that the level of digitalisation is higher in France in the private sector and in Spain in the public sector. In France, this technological transformation led and pushed by big private companies while in Spain the technological transformation is a top – bottom phenomenon, implemented by means of methodologies imposed in the public sector. In the case of the Netherlands, the maturity of the digitalisation of standard services is high in respondent’s perspectives. A decentralisation trend was noticed in this case, with attributions moving away from central level closer to the place of impact. This decentralisation trend is accompanied by the adoption of new legislation for reaching the objectives set in response to climate change. Participants mentioned that new forms of collaborations are needed between the different parties. The market – government relation and their weight for influencing the uptake of climate measures should be further analysed. Digital twins were mentioned as enablers of new forms of collaboration but exchanging information was considered to be cumbersome: “Due to new legislation and new responsibilities with climate change and climate adaptation, municipalities are getting more concerned and aware”. However, size (and implicitly budget) has an impact on performance of achieving the targets with larger cities performing better in the adoption and implementation of these changes. Smaller organizations lack capacity to structurally organize knowledge exchange unless having a dedicated professional interest to do so.

With different forms of technology being available, the challenge moves towards making the technology known, accessible and relevant in a timely fashion to organisations and end users alike. Addressing societal challenges needs a systematic collaborative approach and as one respondent mentions “[looking at] societal challenges and how [those are being approached together with] inhabitants and partners in the society, you see that we're not that well organised”. Volume of available digital tools becomes an issue both for the individual users and the organisations found in the middle, between central level organisations and impacted citizens. It is not the availability of digital solutions that is the issue but rather the discerning between the multitude of existing solutions in a practical fashion. This issue will become even more acute for organisations that face additional challenges that receive must priority.

Digitalisation projects being implemented in a scattered manner across public institutions is another obstacle, with examples in this sense being public administration bodies from Spain

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developing their own data environment, with no coordination, potentially leading to further issues of interoperability. Multiplicity of tools is accompanied by fear of adoption in both private and public sector. Multiple choices and fear of changing way of working created a gap between technological development and technology uptake. Switching between solutions can be expensive with respondents giving the example of real estate companies being approached constantly by tech solution providers offering alternative solutions, something that is considered to “become tiresome”. Organisations will thus prefer the status quo, meaning using the solution that “works. It does the job”, since there is no strong incentive to change: “a lot of [organisations] think that as long as they don't have to change, they won't because there's so much work involved trying to go from one solution to another and it costs a lot of money. So, then they still like they prefer the status quo”. The existence of these high transactional costs is in contrast with what was reported in the Digital Focus Group on civic engagement, where a representative from academia reported having to constantly switch solutions in the academic setting due to price increase.

Community readiness or absorption level of the organizations was identified as a gap by participants and received alignment of experiences from different member states such as the Netherlands and Sweden. Digital maturity does not exclude problems, but has the potential to bring with itself specific challenges, in particular that of interoperability: “there's a lot of problems with interoperability and there are different organizations on very different levels [...] You can have a very mature process within your office or within your organization, but you still have to handle it over in pdf format or in a very immature way. So, you don't really use the whole potential”. A remark connected with the readiness and absorption levels regarded the structural shift or transformation that has taken place in the organisational field. If in the last decades in represented organisations employees performed a good job by following long standing procedures, the current job types require a different orientation: “we need a new repertoire of working”.

Connecting with the comment about absorption levels and community readiness, the respondent being both a representative of a tech company as a solution provider and academic reiterated that level of digitalisation and available digital solutions are not per se the issue, but quite the opposite: the volume of solutions and alternatives and the short timespan for their deployment is what create issues: “there's too much pushing out new ideas and pushing out new technologies towards organizations and people can just not handle all of the new things that are coming to them. There has to be a mechanism that better enables people to absorb these new developments and new technologies”. This perspective received additional support later in the conversation, where respondents added that “technical development is very rapid and you need to be very agile as an organization to be able to take advantage of all these different solutions”.

Respondents reflect on the impact that technology has had on collaboration patterns and power dynamics between local and provincial governments, leading even to conflicts of interests. Introduction of novel technology in a short time span has a disruptive effect on continuous learning and ways of working, which affects technology absorption rates: “that the absorption level [of technology] is so low because we have to find out so many new things in how to work together”. This was contextualised as being a reflection following involvement and awareness of conversations with municipalities, provinces and national government and the educational sector, thus giving more weight to the argument.

One participant with a double role in academia and large company providing digital solutions mentioned that, in their perception, it's not the digitalisation gap in the professional field that is a challenge but rather the behavioural difference. An example in this sense regarded the occasion of a representative of a large tech company going in academic institutions to engage in dialogue about needed digital solutions or common projects, choosing to adapt to the behaviour “of the host”: “We [tech company] are more into tooling. But I actually bought more paper notebooks because it's kind of odd when you meet people and everybody puts their paper notebook in front of them

and then you bring out your iPad or you make notes on your phone. I noted that I changed my behaviour depending on how organizations themselves work with technology. I have these paper notebooks. Then I after the meeting, I take a picture of the notebook. For my notes. So because I'd like to keep things digitized. I do see different behaviour.”

Questioned regarding overlapping alternatives of digital and analogue solutions when it comes to the whole palette of professional needs (in order to determine availability of alternatives in both ways) participants referred to the forming experience that analogue learning has. This was contextualised for the case of creative activities, such as making drawing and mind maps (core competences for the architecture and built environment fields): “I'm more into drawing things and making mind maps and stuff. And I think there is this experience when you draw and when you write that it differs whether that's analogue or digital. And so far, I have not missed anything that I can't do in a digital fashion that is available in an analogue fashion. But when I see organizations work with this, it's quite different.” This opinion aligns with perspectives expressed in other focus groups on the topic of AI literacy skills needing to be predeceased by fundamental and sustained critical thinking experiences in analogue forms. The example of young users of AI solutions relying uncritically on the outputs of the AI system being an example of the risks hereof.

Confirming results from the DFG on education and learning, within the educational sector digital solutions are being used intensively. The digital base, meaning the totality of available and used digital tools within the educational institution is reported as being large: “We get confronted and we use many digital tools. Particularly also in the way we communicate with each other”. This comes with the additional cost of increased workload, as experienced by people: “people experience burden in terms of the workload related to all these different digital systems that are only piling up and increasing the work”. Exacerbating this trend is the known phenomenon of always being connected, or perceived obligation to do so, because the systems, digital solutions and platforms used are always on, always available: “an increasing workload increases the level of things we can get access to. The level of knowledge is getting higher, but the number of hours of work is [also] going much higher”. The perceived threat is that “people cannot cope with the digital solutions that are appearing” and in the education sector, the increase in available digital solutions makes it difficult to integrate them in the educational process. This difficulty then is faced by both students and the tutors who have to include the new digital solutions within their teachings. Due to this exponential increase, “There are less and less possibilities and ways to fully integrate this in education” due to the limited time in which knowledge and skills can be assimilated, what could be called learning fatigue.

AI, one type of digital solution, is mentioned as having the potential to solve the workload issue, but paradoxically, learning how to best use it is a front-loaded activity, requiring more time and energy at the beginning of the learning trajectory. On the use of AI tools, respondents predict that within a three-year timeframe, ways of working will be very different as a result of AI implementation. However, at the current moment, the area of applicability is quite restrictive: “From an architect's point of view, I think there are still not enough good tools [...] at least not in the Swedish market, that you can use to actually draw. You can use them for sketching within city planning [...] For pictures, doing visualizations, it's really powerful already. And if you could just join these two together, which I think will be done and in a couple of years, I think we would probably work differently, drawing within the computer but still prompting things and trying to have totally different process.” More details about the use of AI in professional activities and for facilitating citizen engagement are presented in the following section.

The question on which digitalisation needs should be prioritized was interpreted as promoting a tech push, which was received with resistance by participants that would rather have more conversations on the reasons behind deployment of technology. Respondents again mentioned that it's not possible to prioritize digitalisation needs before knowing what the goal is of what we want

to do: “You should always talk about the goal before you look at what sort of technology you want to use to achieve your goal.”

Fig. 30. Digitalisation needs that should be prioritised.

The open strategic autonomy was interpreted as strategic positioning of Europe “as a democratic continent, [and] different than the US, which is market focus different than China, which is public focused.” The democratic dominant character of Europe seems to be the discussion or consensus seeking model, and participants mentioned that the new Commissioners are instructed to organise and participate in a certain number of events per year with young people, have an open conversation about the future for Europe and talk about the themes in their area. The participants asked for a broader dialogue on inclusivity.

Only when expressly asked if there are any perceived risks regarding this overt openness, was acknowledgment made of the geopolitical risks, from the part of a large digital solution provider: “Publishing open data in the Netherlands for example makes in available almost instantly to states with very different postures, such as Russia and China. The same can be said about technology”. Risk is also perceived in relation with starting a dialogue in the sense of opening the door to uncertainty: “If you have an open conversation, you do not know the outcome”

“There are limits to openness. Although we cherish an open society, there are risks in being too open. And I think for a from a personal perspective, Europe countries in Europe have to determine what those levels of openness are.”

■ 1.4.2 Digital solutions for facilitating engagement

Participants report on the existence of start-ups using AI and AR in order to widen engagement possibilities, (such as co- designing within a platform) but this is reported being only sporadic or in a beta version and not in a wider context.

Swedish research on the digitalisation status of cities in Sweden shows the population is not as inclined to share data openly (RISE, 2024) and suggests that population propensity to share data and engage co-creation strategies something that must be account when planning to deploy such

technologies or engage with the citizens via these strategies. Participants in the DFG looked at the problem from a different angle, reflecting on the way in which such gathered data would be integrated in digital platforms and its subsequent use: “it's very good to collect the data, but if you collect a lot of data, then what would you do with this data? You still need to take decisions that some people won't agree with”. Also, there are already participation processes in place that are not intermediated by technology, but that do allow for citizens to voice their opinions. Even in these processes, citizens can “give you their opinions, but they might not be heard anyway, so I guess that's the more of a problem”. This opinion was backed by another participant, arguing that there is no continuous deep democracy since citizen engagement is sporadic or episodic: “we don't have a situation of continuous deep democracy [...] because it's more cases based. If you have a city plan or something that would be built on, you can have a talk with the citizens, but not in a continuous situation and initiatives like citizen science are incidental and not a continuous valued data stream”. In a vicious circle sort of problem, an additional factor to the problem is that there is currently no theme centric live collecting data around which citizens could debate in such an interactive environment, such as one on light or sound pollution. Integrating these kinds of initiatives and having a centralized overview at municipality or national level is welcomed.

One example of citizen science project is the monitoring of air quality that municipality representatives are interested in. The interest of public institutions in these citizen engagement exercises comes also from the viewpoint of shaping future legislation and policies on the accumulation and use of data: “We [municipality] ask questions about the democratic value and the type of information exchange between the citizens and the municipality or the province [...] because it's interesting to think about when will you use this information and this data as a government. When is it trusted enough and how do you talk about that and how does that relate to new legislation that we expect”.

The representative from the tech company mentioned not seeing AI being integrated in initiatives that are oriented towards the citizen: “Most bigger organizations will have an innovation board as they're doing experiments. The only time I've seen concerns related to citizens is with imagery data. So, one of the AI applications in geospatial is anything that relates to deep learning out of imagery. We see people on imagery and sometimes that means that we don't use that imagery because we would even recognize people if we would. We have to blur them out. You could still kind of know who that would be.”.

In examples coming from the academic environment the same respondent mentioned: “On the design part I see also nice experiments mostly when a university is involved, that really means its experimental. I always have a discussion whether the average citizen, knows how to interpret what they're actually looking at”. Universities themselves mention that they appreciate “the 3D and the fancy tooling” but they are very difficult for the interpretation of what the citizen is actually worried about. The landscape in this direction is evolving, but at a slow pace. Consensus was again expressed with this opinion, mentioning that the use of advanced technologies such as VR for engaging citizens increases expectations that lead to disappointment if opinions are not integrated in the decision-making process or acted upon.

Different forms of engagement with citizens are being experimented with from the public entities in order to test out best practices and results and incorporate those in future approaches, in addition to the concern of interoperability, given that “the Interoperability Act is coming and we are thinking about multilevel governance and then it is interesting if we can include citizen science or other types of decentralized science in the information exchange and in monitoring what's happen”.

It comes across that currently these engagement technologies are better performing in pilot projects, as opinions in this direction abounded. VR and AR are used intensely in the educational sector, and students use them for their final projects. Applicability areas include post occupancy and

inquiries for transformation areas, with case studies from the Netherlands, the Czech Republic, Poland. Also in these cases, “the most problematic part is the level of preparedness needed for individuals to access and use these digital solutions. These challenges are easier overcome in larger projects or controlled environments where there is more time to learn and prepare. “Augmented reality and virtual reality developed in pilot projects, sometimes related to faculty and sometimes with public administration” A mentioned example is from France, in a project involving teachers in the designing of high schools by means of virtual reality and augmented reality on the design part. Interaction with this technology was not difficult due to access to this technology for leisure purposes and as such AR could be implemented easily nowadays in society. There were opposite views during the discussions on the appropriateness of advanced technologies in controlled environments vs. in society as a whole, with more opinions being expressed in the direction of suitability in controlled environments, the argument being that in a non-controlled environment it can be very disruptive and not easy to absorb.

The aspect of level of preparedness was contested by another participant, mentioning that young people acquire more easily the skills needed for new technologies. On a different note, acquiring the skills needed to use a specific tool for a very specific problem or only test that tool for a while can prove unproductive if its use is limited in time and applicability and not transferable. Even as a professional, having and maintaining an overview of all available solutions is a time-consuming activity and one cannot know if the picture obtained at a certain time is complete.

Given these trends, there is a need for more knowledge on “societal readiness to know how to organize a more mature conversation with all stakeholders in cities, not only the inhabitants, but also companies”.

■ 1.4.3 Connecting Digitalisation to the Green Deal

Legislation can be a push factor for digitalisation, as explained in the following example. Obligations on measuring emissions were introduced by way of legislation in some countries and in practice measuring contributes to faster and founded decision making. If national legislations, as that introduced in Sweden 2022 according to participants, require carbon dioxide levels related to a building to be declared, in practice, making holistic calculations of these rates is difficult in the absence of digital solutions, as related by expert in the field: “as an architect and within the industry it's almost impossible not to do it [the calculation] without the higher level or maturity of digitalization”. The legislation referred to here was considered to having contributed a lot to the digitalisation levels since entities were forced to increase their digitalisation.

Professional and policy makers at different levels engage in dialogues about manners of digitalisation. The related conversations indicate that the debate is active within the community, signalling the existence of challenges and different views on best approaches for implementation of digitalisation actions and accompanying legislation. This is also connected to the fact that new technology in itself can increase pollution or energy consumption (a concrete example being discussed in the section dedicated on AI, that is known to be a highly energy consuming technology). “It's quite a challenge to have a good balance because new technology is polluting in itself as well. To then contribute to a greener environment, that's quite a balance to look after.” This challenge of adopting digital solutions that add to energy consumption and pollution emissions while at the same time trying to achieve the objectives of bringing down emissions received additional acknowledgement from participant, shaping as a visible trend.

Other participants reflect on the change in perception that has taken place in relation to targets of digitalisation and the Green Deal: “when I started working on BIM projects, I was quite sceptical about the link between both (digitalisation and sustainability and greening objectives), considering it even “brainwashing”. In time however, the perception changed, as collected data contributes to

saving energy. Additionally, the change in mindset related to the digital twin represented a paradigm shift, where thinking holistically, in a whole lifecycle approach about the building of cities links technology with better management of the environment: “When you start thinking about projects or buildings, or cities, not just as a product, but also as the whole life cycle where you need to implement these technologies. This helps, as everything is related to the better management of the environment”. This change of mindset regarding the twin transition was strongly criticized towards the end of the discussion, with the policy being characterised as marketing, with the upcoming of a triple transition: green, digital and multi-governance, that is influenced politically.

Reaching the objectives of the Green Deal requires a collaborative approach at European level. Reflecting on the role, objective and means of implementation of the Green Deal, a participant representing municipalities in the Netherlands mentions that “The Green Deal [is] a mission that is not really bordered by countries. If we really want to do it, then we have to team up as Europe, as a grid of concern about nature and pollution etc.” The logic and need of combining the digital transition with the Green Deal were acknowledged during the discussion, with detailed references to the official position of the European Commission, indicating awareness of the programme at national, central and regional levels: “I heard the European Commission talking a lot about the twin transition and then they were talking about the fact that we can't do the Green Deal without the digital transition. [...] It has to be combined and at the same time there's a tension if you look at the footprint of digital solutions”.

Respondents mention that the European policy level is currently being transposed at national levels, with discussions “now starting up in the Gov.Tech part” in the Netherlands. The Digital Decade Pyramid (see Figure 31) was also referenced in the discussions as an instrument that will be reviewed in order to make a stronger connection between new legislation and the Missions in the Green Deal. In this regard, the Interoperability Act was considered as one of the enablers of multi-governance monitoring of the Green Deal objectives. However, these objectives were criticised in terms of the feasibility for their accomplishment in the coming years. The matter was put in relation with the societal redness, arguing that “our surroundings are more ready for this type of solutions or the people that are concerned are more ready for this type of solutions than the organizations that we're working in”. Respondents thus opinionated that the objectives of the Green Deal, at this moment in time, are easier to approach in a bottom-up approach, due to less friction with mature organisational structures that might have to go through costly or cumbersome changes in order to reach such objectives. These are not unsurmountable challenges since the expressed opinion was that “we see that as a tension or potential conversation or dialogue in how to organize that.”

Fig. 31. The Digital Decade pyramid, referenced by participants in the focus group discussions.

Source: [European Commission](#) (2024)

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Fig. 32. Quotes from the DFG on digital solutions. Part 1.

■ 1.4.4 Future priorities of the NEB and the impact of the current geopolitical context

Named areas of priority included type of following: “There should be more and more attention in terms of funding for small projects, local projects, local communities, empowering and bridging the gaps that you also sketched in your previous comments. [...] fine tune the type of funding to that type of project, perhaps even towards seed money projects, small projects that could, let's say, get a result on very specific areas”. Raising awareness about success projects from different member

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states and fine tune or increase the impact of these bottom-up initiatives would be beneficial: “There are some exemplary projects where people are sharing knowledge about their neighbourhoods, about the actions of what they do in certain areas [that] are not completely fine-tuned with what authorities are trying to organise, or trying to master, to controlling or advance”. Better connection between citizen and authorities was also mentioned: “Getting neighbourhoods organised on semi organised together with local authorities and facilitating this type of conversation also through digital channels”.

Better showcasing the results of projects financed by the Commission and their impact is recommended. Speaking from experience based on conversations with educators, students, professionals such as geo professionals, one participant mentioned that in these circles the Green Deal or Horizon project are seen as being just that – projects, with a finite duration and therefore “the impact is often viewed as questionable, not practical”. Students participating in such project experience them as research that is disconnected from real life work. Therefore, when talking about projects, “impact must be measurable, must be communicated and must be felt by the people involved, by citizens as well”.

In response to the question of the impact that the geopolitical context on the NEB priorities, information was asked from participants. Extreme right political movements that are taking up in Europe are perceived as having the potential to have an impact on climate change initiatives, with examples from Spain being given where change in economic priorities have an impact on educational institutions and innovation programmes. This opinion received support from other participants, the Draghi report being mentioned in this regard.

The revaluation that the Commission made in 2023 to the NEB programme was mentioned in detail and positively appreciated in terms of a novel focus: “When we looked at the new European Bauhaus and especially at the way that the Commission evaluated the horizon programs and the Green Deal Objectives that were described in Horizon programmes and were evaluated by the European Commission in the summer of '23 [we found them] very interesting because the Commission said that we are focusing too much on technology and we're not making the necessary change if we keep doing it like this. So, we need more transformation power and we need to think more about how to organize that. The New European Bauhaus was a sort of hope for this transformational journey and thinking about values like sustainability, inclusion, aesthetics as a new way of opening up and having a broader conversation beyond our [close] network”. This focus on the network was positively appreciated by other participants in the Digital Focus Group.

A sentiment of distrust was mentioned in relation to how people relate to the weight their opinions have in the European decision-making process: “If you look at the political sentiment in Europe at this moment, there's a lot of distrust and fear. Europe is, at least it's a sort of image, that it's a technocratic decision-making system and that people don't feel that they can influence the outcome of the system, and that probably there's a connection between the trust issue and the feeling that they don't have influence on the end results. And that makes it even more important to focus on the implicit values that we see.” There is therefore the challenge of externalities on the priority setting of the NEB and in the same time a legacy that influences how people react to the NEB that has to be addressed. The program will have to balance somehow these initiatives.

“Tech[nology] in itself is a power agent”. Reflecting on the role of technology and the power that big tech companies have”, a respondent gave the example of the initiative taken by the Australian government to ban social media for young people under the age of 16. In the case of big social media platforms, data is their business, as opposed to a technology firm where you can buy or rent the technology or choose a different supplier, because there are alternatives. In the case of social media companies, the choice that citizens have is much smaller, if at all available, as participants reflect.

When looking at innovation ecosystems, one question that should be addressed according to participants is who is being excluded from the conversation. Debating on the topic of the role technology plays in the democratization process and the limits of this relationship (due to different bargaining power between developers and deployers, costs, vendor lock-ins etc.) participant mentioned that every technology creates lock in, that just needs to be managed. Participants are also critical of the word association “democracy” and “technology” because there is a “either or” side of this.

Reflections on the ethics and the political side of technology were expressed: “we always have to debate around new technologies to keep them democratic. That’s a tension we have to work on about tech ethics. The value systems that are brought into that technology are important to know”. Participants express that more research on tech ethics is needed as technology is evolving too quickly and there is not enough time to analyse its impact. When confronted with the idea that the Dutch polder model of consensus-based agreement on how technology is being deployed might not be characteristic for other EU member states when it comes to technology deployment, participants mentioned that in their view approaches across the EU are consistent, and more different when compared with approaches and practices from the North America or Asia, examples being stance on open data, open formats, data exchange. Additional reflections included the fact that a step prior to the physically possible deployment of technology should be an ethical reflection on the desirability of doing so: Sometimes we step into things without taking a moment to look back. [and ask] is this really what we ought to do? [...] Technology wise, data wise it is possible. What does it really bring us? What are the risks involved? What does it mean on a personal level?”.

These reflections align with previous opinions from other focus groups that digitalisation in itself is not the purpose and should not be followed as such. Claiming open discussion on the “Why” should be prioritized in front of initiatives focusing on digitalisation uptake, participants plea for more horizontal communication, seeing this as a benefit. An example of constructive dialogue was related to use of drones where the position “We have drones. Let’s use them” should be anticipated by a discussion over the need of the deployment, the “Why”. Further agreement was expressed in this regard, arguing that the tech push should be counterbalanced with more reflection exercises.

The question on enablers of technology was received was answered by turning back to the topic of ethics and values. Offering a reflective observation regarding the type of answers that the question on enablers of technology received, namely reflections over ethics, one respondent mentioned that such discussions around the ethics of technological deployment can represent enablers of technological development in an unexpected way. Dialogue over ethics could thus have a nudging function for a broader discussion on digitalisation.

“We are more into tooling. But I actually bought more paper notebooks because it's kind of odd when you meet people and everybody puts their paper notebook in front of them and then you bring out your iPad or you make notes on your phone. I noted that I changed my behaviour depending on how organizations themselves work with technology. I have these paper notebooks. Then I after the meeting, I take a picture of the notebook. For my notes. So because I'd like to keep things digitized. I do see different behaviour.”[large technology provider].

“There are limits to openness. Although we cherish an open society, there are risks in being too open. And I think for a from a personal perspective, Europe countries in Europe have to determine what those levels of openness are.”

“Tech is politics”

“there's too much pushing out new ideas and pushing out new technologies towards organizations, and its people can just not handle all of the new things that are coming to them. There has to be a mechanism that better enables people to absorb these new developments and new technologies “

Fig. 33. Quotes from the DFG on digital solutions. Part 2

○ 1.5 Digital Focus Group on Bio Based Materials

The Digital Focus Group on Bio-based Materials took place in October. In this case, recruitment was based on desk research, identification of relevant actors from the umbrella project partner – Innovawood and snowball sampling. Response rates were much lower than in the other Digital Focus Groups and a number of 3 organisations participated in the live discussion. The organisations represented by the participants were form the Netherlands, Spain, the UK and Belgium. In order to

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compensate for this lower volume of data collection, additional data collection was planned via the initial interactive Miro Board, in order to add layers of information and enrich the collected input. Additionally, representatives from the bio-based materials sector were present in the Digital Focus Group on civic engagement, and challenges they mention that are specific to their sector are presented in the sub-chapter dedicated to the Digital Focus Group on civic engagement.

As was the case in the other Digital Focus Groups, some participants wore multiple hats, being active in different organizations. Participants were from multinational companies with the headquarters in the Netherlands, developing international projects in the EU, Middle East, China, Australia; Institute of Architecture and educational organisations from Spain and the UK, umbrella organisation in the area of wood research, innovation and education. Additional area of activities included forest management, developing modular facades, reused timber, timber structures and included the use of BIM, CAD, CAE. Activities conducted by one participant included educational activities with “students studying architecture to familiarize them with the entire value chain of timber as a bio-based material and they then use the products from that forest management to produce what we call advanced ecological prototype buildings. So engineered timber buildings, but also integrating circular water systems, renewable energy systems and so forth.” Research activities mentioned by one participant include focused on “studying different bio-based value chains for architecture as social ecological networks, which essentially means mapping all of the stakeholders involved and the ecosystem. They extract resources from to diagram those relationships.”

Given these areas of activities, the sample of participants is considered representative in terms of content for the investigated theme. Additionally on several occasions, the respondents expressed agreement with the others participants interventions, therefore strengthening the representativeness of the responses.

Fig. 34. Content analysis - DFG Bio Based materials

■ 1.5.1 The main challenges when it comes to using the available digital solutions

According to participants, the perceived challenges regarding the existing digital solutions are influenced by professional experiences and points of view, and might differ between architects and engineers. One identified challenge is that the existing solutions do not cover the entire process of the design phase: “talking about wood construction, but mainly focusing on timber structures [...] there is a gap or a lack of knowledge [between] when the BIM model is designed and then you need to develop the structural model. So, there is no good correlation between the BIM model and the 3D structural design for obtaining the size of the elements. This is one of the gaps I can see in the whole process.”

Material passports, identified in the desk research phase and included in the intermediary roadmap as a topic for further investigation was brought up in the discussion by participants: “the topic of material passports that we talk about often is significant, especially because of potentials for circularity in the future, being able to understand where materials are in space and time so that we can ensure that they're reused if we're trying to maximize the benefit of the biogenic carbon in our structures. We need to make sure that we're designing at least components that last upwards of 100 years if the buildings don't.”

The matter of skills was also addressed in connection with the digital solutions available and the ones still needed. The digitally born have an advantage over the generation that needed to learn how to use digital tools while in the field, the second category running the risk of staying behind if they do not acquire the needed skills. The gap that needs to be breached is represented by these differences in skill levels influenced by generational elements. This perspective received support from the other participants in the discussion and was linked to the challenge of reaching the objectives of the Green Deal, as detailed in the next section.

■ 1.5.2 Digitalisation and the targets of the Green Deal

The existence of digital tools is confirmed to contribute to the objectives of the Green Deal but the skills gap is one hindering factor in the uptake of digital solutions:

“the life cycle assessment tools that we have available contribute towards the Green Deal, but there are some challenges or barriers to those, especially their adoption amongst architects in the design phase. There's still a practice in which these are used as assessments after design and then retroactive, fixing of designs to improve those LCAs, but many architects are not trained into how to use LCAs even the simpler systems like one click. And having that kind of training or having more fluid tools will allow them to be more iterative design tools to actually influence the way that these buildings are conceived. But then of course, even within the LCA system, there are needs for improvement in the reliability of environmental product declarations with this shift also towards environmental footprint, we need to make sure that that data is reliable.”

In the case of structural design with bio-based solutions, such as timber, there is a knowledge gap in working with this kind of material: “it's very difficult when you try to design with some innovative product. [It] is good because the life cycle assessment works better with these materials and you can design OK an architectural design but when you need to do the structural design, you don't have enough information to model this material because there are no standards yet.”

Most of timber construction are based in soft species, if you would like to design with hardwood, because it's nice and aesthetically, or with oak or chestnut, it's really, really complicated because you

don't have this information. [...] Structural designers don't know about these materials and if you go deeper when you are designing complex structures and you need to design using finite element modelling it's even worse. There is no standard. There are no books, there is no information how to design with these materials. So sometimes the life cycle assessment can [be done by design instructors], but then the structural designers have a problem because they don't know how to do it. So there is a gap between this flow between designers, Green Deal and structural design”.

An example of digital tool used to measure carbon emissions is the “carbon builder”. The data of the building is ingested by the system, including details such as the size of the building, the location, intended materials to be used and based on the given parameters the analysis of the carbon emissions for a building is useful for both designers and the client.

Initiatives on digitalisation that contribute to the targets of the Green Deal should also look upstream:

“The relationship between forests, generally providing the materials that give us low carbon buildings. Of course, there's multiple sources, but simply achieving a holistic model for the relationship, even in Europe, between forest extraction and management and the amount of timber or other forest-based products that we have available to build with, is a large knowledge gap. I know there are other horizon projects working on those models. The Forest Pass project in particular. Yeah, but if we're trying to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, we need to consider our sinks in store as much as our buildings, we need to understand what the effect of making carbon neutral buildings has on the ecosystems that provide those materials”

This perspective was supported by other participants who also added that there is an additional need for standards in the case of reused materials, for knowing the mechanical properties of the claimed or reused wood. On the topic of reused materials, not only standards are needed but also “some instruments, whether legal or otherwise, to ensure that materials designed for reuse are in fact reused. What we see in common practice often is that maybe antiquarians who are searching for a particularly valuable used object will maintain them in their integrity, in their entire state, but generally for contractors disassembling buildings, it's faster simply to cut off joints and connections, even if they're designed to be disassembled. So we have a design question, but we also have the practice question.”

These instruments reflect the need for prioritizing potentially conflicting values, processes and roles in the chain, considering that projects always run against tight deadlines.

AI use for making the regenerative sector more affordable is rather limited, being introduced recently in participants organisations, mainly for producing design images. Participants mentioned that to their knowledge there is no AI tool for making the regenerative construction more affordable:

“Generally [...] generative AI is used to produce images that are conceptual inspirational but then if they are implemented, they require some translation. I think there's potential [...] about grading secondary materials, maybe not for AI so much as machine learning or computer vision to help with grading those materials that could improve the affordability of structures.” However, this application is limited to the research area, not in practice.

Other examples of digital solutions for enabling communication between different entities were [Decidim](#) and a gamified platform:

“there's a fantastic example digital platform for participatory processes called Decidim that started in Catalonia. I think it's now been adopted by New York City as well as a few other major metro areas. That has various different tools, some map-based interfaces as well as chat, forums and so forth for people to propose ideas and try and prioritize built environment interventions.”

“These kinds of digital platforms are great in terms of reaching a broad spectrum of people, but of course, we also have to be a bit cautious about who has access to digital platforms. It might prioritize those who are digitally literate as opposed to, say, younger people, or maybe elderly people who have limited access to these tools or limited awareness.”

“There's also some interesting, more gamified versions of this that I'd say are more experimental, but yak, for instance, has a project called Super Buddy that is also a sort of 3D mapped based. Story platform, but in a setting that looks a lot like Sims, so you don't need much.”

With the examples of initiatives for improving citizen engagement comes a cautionary tale. Focusing on total numbers misses addressing meaningful interaction and structural improvements such as addressing low literacy levels.

■ 1.5.3 Incentives, market dynamics and hindering factors for sustainable building practices

Cost is a major factor when selecting a construction material:

“Cost is always a big one, and sometimes you see that some people are not always open for it. [...] People don't want to have a facade that was used for another building before. It's sometimes difficult to really convince a client. Even if it's not more expensive. Sometimes we don't talk about sustainability but more about improving people's life and then we come to a more sustainable material”.

There is also a certain reluctance regarding the use of bio-based materials from the side of the client: “Sometimes clients don't want to use it. So if we talk about sustainability we have to reframe it”. The manner in which the project is presented to the stakeholders in order to raise support is important: “sometimes an active component is more costly, but maybe over the long run you also generate some money out of it or save some money out of it.”

The type of materials used in the construction sector is also determined by the traditions in a certain country: “in a country without tradition in building, not with reclaim or similar material, but also just with sustainable materials which are not concrete or steel, sometimes it's really difficult to convince people.” This opinion is grounded on the experience of designing timber structures in Spain and in Uruguay, South America.

Another respondent reported it was easier to introduce sustainable materials when they also presented an aesthetic component. The cost is important, but ultimately it depends on the end users. Cultural factors and traditions have an impact on the material choices made in the built environment. “If there is no tradition for the use of these kind of materials, it is difficult [to convince clients to adopt it].” Additional remarks were that “wood is associated with poor people” and thus it becomes a challenge to convince people that “wood is cool” and wood is associated with the southern countries.

Aesthetics, social impact, and long-term impact were mentioned as criteria for choosing a certain type of material. Additional arguments included technical elements of the material, including light weight and adaptability of these materials, which make extensions of existing building possible. As hindering factor, the difficulty to have an insurance policy for wood structures was mentioned.

“There are certainly projects where the biophilic benefits of natural materials are important for the clients. We see that often in Catalonia with social housing projects. If they're led by cooperatives, often they prefer these materials because of their aesthetic and the impression that they support health and well-being. In addition to environmental benefits [...] even though everything has relationships to economics, the adaptability of bio-based materials [is relevant]. The fact

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that they're lighter weight and therefore might create opportunities for changing layouts over time that other materials have more difficulty with. This is something that we're investigating in terms of using timber to add stories on top of existing buildings, again taking advantage of that lightweightness so. Yes, there are some technical aspects besides economic aspects that are important”.

Durability is another influencing factor: “people need to be sure that it will be durable [...] at least as much as concrete”. For this reason “it's easier to introduce these kind of materials in combination with this mature materials” such as concrete. In order to “convince people it is efficient and secure.”

Europe is seen as a leader in wood and timber construction: “all knowledge and standards come from Europe. Europe needs to provide these standards and this knowledge to other countries outside Europe and then the other countries can develop their own way”. This was again a point that other participants expressed agreement with.

■ 1.5.4 Incentives for decarbonization

Respondents were asked if current financial opportunities are well-equipped or visible enough to address the needs of SMEs and their decarbonization efforts. The existence of these financing mechanisms was acknowledged, but their visibility is low and acquiring such funding is influenced by the effort put in by companies in finding such funding opportunities.

In the case of retrofitting activities, these are mostly targeted at residents of homeowners, not at SMEs and as such more financial initiatives dedicated to SMEs would be beneficial: “there are certainly opportunities, but [...] we could benefit from more. I think it's insightful to ask about SMEs, in particular, at least in Barcelona, many of the opportunities are targeted towards citizens and residents, for example, we have many grants. For energy retrofit, which are fantastic, they are by definition limited to residents or homeowners. So I think more mechanisms targeted towards SMEs would be beneficial.”

SMEs benefit from the use of digital solutions are used for estimating costs and carbon footprints of buildings using bio-based materials: “digital tools have a role to play here. [...] thinking about some of our own projects in terms of helping. Developers or SMEs understand what the potential economic benefits of choosing the bio-based material are. [...] this project of adding vertical stories on top of existing buildings can be more cost effective. So, we're trying to develop digital tools that give an early estimation of what those numbers might work out to”.

This last-mentioned tool is embedded in a project between Spain, the Netherlands and the UK: “using very basic structural engineering and different typologies of buildings. So that an asset owner can input some simple information about their property and based on the structural typology and the area, get a quick guess of how much area they could add. Using a modular timber system”. The structural capacity is only one factor and the complexity of the project is influenced by the complexity of regulations.

Giving examples from Spain, a respondent acknowledged the existence of some funding mechanism for different types of entities, adding that there are government initiatives, policies and strategies for boosting the use of your bio-based materials, mainly wood and also for training, taking into account the carbon storage. These are however not common.

The carbon builder was mentioned again as example of digital solution used as decision facilitator when considering alternative designs for different material choices, thus reducing the carbon footprint.

Other examples of non-financial initiatives for stimulating the use of bio-based materials come from the UK, where regional and local councils implemented “wood first” programs, such as the Hackney Council. These “can help SMEs accelerate permitting processes. They're generally not economic - they don't receive payment or grants, but they're able to get through regulatory processes more quickly.”

Material passport infrastructure was given as example of initiatives that can be implemented for better collection structuring, processing and use of data in order to increase circularity in buildings.

Asked what are the present principal needs for the sector in order to become more sustainable and decarbonize and the incentives or for enhancing rates of decarbonization, participants first expressed their belief that this was a very important question and subsequently addressed the aspect of carbon pricing: “Among the most important is carbon taxing or appropriate pricing of carbon to ensure that the economics actually balance out for bio-based materials. We need to somehow account for what have been externalities in the past in terms of the environmental consequences of building with highly emissive materials.” The relevance of this point is sustained by the intense debates of the COP29 Climate Conference in Baku (2024) that required extra time for negotiation of a global agreement. Approaches to decarbonization should be holistic and complementary. Size of a sector influences the perceived relevance of introducing initiatives in that certain segment. Example in this sense is the market share of wood based constructions compared to concrete buildings and the impact of each on carbon emissions: “some say that wood materials is only 3% of the materials used for building in Europe. If the concrete lobby does something minimal to decrease the carbon consumption or other energy consumption, it will impact [the targets] much more than what we can do with bio-based materials so”.

Decarbonisation initiatives should also be implemented in the other sectors, such as the concrete constructions one, because initiatives here will have a higher impact due to the larger market share of this segment. Connecting the material with the environment – such as is the case of wood being connected to the forest was also mentioned, as wood captures carbon.

Emphasising the positive effects of decarbonisation actions was further mentioned: “besides economic benefits, it's improving health. In a sustainable building you create better air quality, lower levels of toxins. So you enhance the well-being of community and maybe also even promoting local resources.” Relying on shorter supply chains, using local materials is also mentioned.

On the topic of the length of the supply chain, and the cascading effects of long supply chains, respondents mentioned the following effects on the goals of the Green Deal:

“Supply chain development is essential when you think about the supply and the demand sides. So in terms of demand, we're talking about making carbon emissive materials less attractive, but also, timber is still an incredibly small market share: besides 3% in Europe, only about 1 to 1.5% of buildings in Spain are timber based. So, these value chains simply don't exist at the scale to meet the demand for new buildings yet. So, there's a huge acceleration that needs to happen in that throughput if we actually want to satisfy the need for new buildings with these lower carbon materials unless we rely on very long supply chains. Currently the buildings that are made import from the [...] region or from Scandinavia. So, if we're trying to create also regionally and resilient economies, but also benefit from the other ecosystem services that my peers here have mentioned, whether that's health and well-being or water quality, air quality, etcetera. we don't receive those benefits locally if the supply chains are international.” One respondent reported on a new trend in Spain on “using wood from 0 kilometres”, with manufacturers from Catalunya, Galicia and Basque country adopting this trend. This is in opposition to material acquisition and consumption patterns and supply chains from 20 or 30 years prior, when most timber used in factories in Spain came from Northern Europe. Connecting with the topic of global or long supply chains the next question

investigated respondent's perception of the consequences of geopolitical changes on the NEB and the European Green Deal.

■ 1.5.5 Future NEB prioritises

Political agendas shape the priorities of public policies and in more subtle ways, the interpretation of existing initiatives, such as the ones developed for inclusion purposes:

"[It will] absolutely [have an impact]. We're already seeing some impacts if we think about the NEB priorities of beauty, inclusion, sustainability. Any political change that influences climate research and innovation funding has a direct impact. We are seeing this, for instance, in Sweden with the rise of the conservative right and the impacts on climate funding, but we see it also from the social angle again with fears about immigration and so forth. When we consider inclusion, it raises the question of inclusion for whom? When we design these projects, we also see it in Catalonia locally in terms of fear of over tourism. Does inclusion mean everybody who uses the city or does it mean serving the local population? They can both be interpreted as inclusion, but I think that interpretation depends heavily on political priorities."

On the matter of redirecting funds from the NEB to other priority areas, the respondent held back on expressing a definite point of view. "That has to do with the ambiguity of the future of the NEB overall. It's fantastic that we have the NEB facility being established and these scoping documents and these recent calls for input, but from an external perspective, as a beneficiary of NEB funds but not being integrated in establishing the NEB facility, it's still unclear what the future looks like for the NEB facility, so it's hard to know how geopolitics will change that."

Answers on what the priorities of the NEB should be included:

- Prioritizing regenerative bio-based materials for construction and regional value chains to produce those.
- Focus more on wood.
- Focus on quality of life. Quality of life for the residents, improving public spaces, access to nature, even if it's in the building; community centric design.

Fig. 35. QUOTES – DFG – Bio-Based materials

■ 1.5.6 MIRO Board input

The input provided by participants in the MIRO board is presented in the following. In this DFG there were considerably more open questions addressed in the MIRO board, as objectives in the new NEB programme on the topic of bio-based materials were much clearer defined in the official document policies used for defining the research objectives during the desk research phase and mentioned above.

Enablers of technological innovation are:

- Funding;
- Education;
- R&D;
- Market demand;
- Regulatory framework/support;
- Research;
- Interdisciplinary approach;
- Benefits identified;
- Commercial interest-exploitation'
- R&D + funding;
- Collaboration across disciplines and geographies;
- Joint tenders;
- Performance-based regulation (as opposed to prescriptive);
- Acceptance of failure (e.g. 'moonshots')

Fig. 36. Enablers of technological innovation. DFG focus on Bio-based materials.

Examples of initiatives for increasing the re-use and re-purposing of materials, building elements, buildings and public spaces towards circularity in construction, based on reversible building design and sufficiency include:

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

- “Building on top” (vertical extension of existing structures)
- High-quality warehouses/markets for secondary materials (e.g. Ombygg in Oslo)
- material banks, deconstruction guidelines, modular building design, showcasing circular in public infrastructure
- Methodologies for urban mining (e.g. Superuse Studios publications)
- Strategies for regional circular bio-based industry and value chain development (e.g. Material Cultures publications)
- Innovative reversible joint/connection systems (e.g. HasleTre in Oslo, Birk Heilmeyer und Frenzel Architekten in Stuttgart)

Fig. 37. Examples of initiatives for increasing the re-use and re-purposing of materials, building elements, buildings and public spaces towards circularity in construction, based on reversible building design and sufficiency. DFG Focus on biobased materials.

Respondents gave the following examples of innovative bio-based regenerative construction materials for structural and exterior architecture:

- Innovative timber products for structural applications: Hardwoods glulam, Composites (GLT-CLT), Timber-concrete composites (TCC), Parallel strand lumber (using secondary products from sawmills), Wood connectors, adhesive and steel-free timber slabs, etc.;
- Insulation materials: wood-based (fibre, cellulose,...), mycelium, etc.;
- Mature timber products (GLT, CLT, softwoods);
- wood, bamboo, cork, rammed earth recycled plastics;
- Engineered timber and bamboo;
- 3D-printed earth;
- Cellulose/mycelium etc. insulation;
- Agri/aqua-culture waste products (e.g. sugar beet fiber insulation, mussel beard acoustic panels, oyster shell tiles, etc.);
- Hempcrete, mycelium blocks;
- Post-tensioned stone.

Fig. 38 Examples of innovative bio-based regenerative construction materials for structural and exterior architecture. DFG on bio-based materials.

Examples of innovative supply chains – taking the cascading principle - that transform waste materials into high-quality secondary construction materials and products included:

- Parallel strand lumber (PSL)
- Honext board (from recycled cellulosic residues)
- ECO-WÜRTERMIC (80% recycled cotton)
- plastic waste transformation, glass recycling, recycled concrete, textile recycling
- Mussel beards for acoustic insulation panels (Seastex in London)
- Wood fibre insulation

Fig. 39 Examples of innovative supply chains – taking the cascading principle - that transform waste materials into high-quality secondary construction materials and products.

Unlike in the other DFG, the question on digitalisation needs that should be prioritized was introduced as an open-ended question. This proved to bring a richer and more diverse input that can be incorporated in future policy documents.

Digitalisation needs that should be prioritized:

- collaboration tools, data management SharePoint, BIM, user experience;
- Improve the exchange between CAD/CAM/BIM models and structural design models;
- Integration between LCA software and structural design software;
- Optimisation in the design to be resource efficient (less material), but also considering the potential of carbon storage of wood in buildings
- LCA tools integrated w/ design processes (i.e. One Click LCA > BIM)
- Material passports
- Tools for quickly assessing economic or strategic opportunities (e.g. vertical extensions to existing structures)
- Reference databases of enabling policies, best practices, case studies, etc.

Fig. 40 Digitalisation needs that should be prioritized. DFG focus on bio-based materials.

Examples of innovative use of by-products and secondary bio-based materials (including re-claimed wood) were:

- wood chips, recycled paper, date palm waste
- Engineered timber products incorporating secondary wood
- Wood fibre insulation
- Mussel beards for acoustic insulation panels (Seastex in London)

Fig. 41. Examples of innovative use of by-products and secondary bio-based materials (including reclaimed wood). DFG focus on bio-based materials.

Respondents gave the following examples of social, aesthetic, and economic impacts of carbon-sequestering materials in the built environment:

- Social housing: Cornellá sponsored housing (Avda. Republica Argentina 21, Cornellá de Llobregat, Spain);
- MACA Museum (Uruguay);
- Social housing projects in Barcelona (e.g. La Borda, Terrazas para la Vida, etc.);
- cost saving, health benefits, natural surroundings;
- Research on health and wellbeing benefits of exposed wood (i.e. phytoncides);
- Gabriel García Márquez library in Barcelona;
- Cost savings due to accelerated/efficient construction timelines (e.g. Murray Grove, Treet building).

Fig. 42. Examples of social, aesthetic, and economic impacts of carbon-sequestering materials in the built environment. DFG focus on bio-based materials.

The main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe are:

- The growth of a circular and regenerative construction sector
- The digital transformation
- The green transition

Fig. 43. The main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe. DFG focus on bio-based materials.

Respondents also listed several other factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe, namely:

- Regional strategic planning for circular bio-based value chains;
- Energy, infrastructure, talent, finance;
- Education and immigration to mitigate aging;
- Education for skills in designing with bio-based materials;
- Update standards and regulations for circularity in construction materials;
- Resource efficiency in the design to get a balanced wood supply-demand;
- Promote the cascade use of wood, avoiding wood for energy as main use.

Fig. 44. Other factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe.

On the matter of the visibility of the initiatives for open strategic autonomy and the coherence of the included initiatives, the response was that regional autonomy is more visible and European autonomy is not that often part of the discussion: “[...] open strategic autonomy at the European level honestly doesn't come up much. We often discuss regional autonomy. But I would say in the projects I engage with, the idea of European autonomy is not highly prioritized”. It seems thus that OSA is more of a central policy level concern.

● 2. Gap analysis

○ 2.1 Digitalisation trends and gaps

- Identified challenges regarding the current status of digitalisation include interoperability of solutions, cascading effects of technological choices, innovation in silos, fragmentation, high volume of solutions and no user-friendly instrument facilitating choice.
- National levels of digitalization are reflected in sector-specific levels of digital solution adaptation. Even if levels of digitalisation are high, adopting a digital solution should be fit for purpose and a choice, not a top-down imposition or a reaction to a hype trend. As technical choices can have cascading effects, the issue of interoperability must be kept in mind whenever undertaking new digitalisation projects.
- Digitalisation is not consumed only homogeneously or amorphy; it is also *experienced* in a holistic way and the importance of using system thinking when looking at digitalisation trends and the built environment must be stressed. This requires a shift towards a systematic approach for enabling and enhancing synergies, making system interactions and dependencies visible.
- Collaborative, adaptive, digital mapping solutions for changing needs and changing environments are needed. Digitalisation regeneration by means of digitizing the public space for stimulating interaction and digital inclusion is encouraged.
- Volumes of digital solutions become cumbersome for users who, while lacking a systematized solution or quality filter for choosing the right tool for their needs, have to navigate through repetitive information sources and alternatives that bring no decisive edge for quickly choosing a solution.
- A helicopter overview of existing solutions is either lacking or not visible enough inside the practitioner's community.
- Initiatives on digitalisation should not be limited to the conceptual, construction or repurposing phases. They should also include data capture during post-occupancy in order to make living spaces continuously adaptive environments.
- Innovation in silos is another challenge, with upscaling of solutions becoming difficult.
- With the diversification of available digital solutions, the challenge of interoperability becomes greater and greater.
- An additional factor that hinders interoperability is the high cost of switching between digital solution or solution providers.
- AI, digital tools and data processing capabilities have a transformative effect on the workplace, and as they also become available to more and more people, their accumulated volume of changed patterns of behaviour feeds back into the change pattern, exacerbating it.

- The aging of the population is one aspect that the NEB should focus on, deploying digital solutions to address these challenges, including the use of AI and robotic solutions for combating loneliness, facilitating care work and making living environments at different scales accessible to elderly individuals with mobility difficulties. The use of AI in the lived environment – the home – in order to transform the environment in a learning and adaptive one is appreciated.
- Novel technologies such as VR or AI are best deployed in projects or controlled environments where there is more time to learn and prepare.

○ 2.2 Digital solutions for Civic engagement

- There is discrepancy across the EU landscape regarding the use of technologies for enabling citizen engagement showing fragmentation in practices and, we might argue, the fact that visibility of certain initiatives is hindered by the combination of high volume and small scale of these initiatives.
- Similar to the perception on the limited impact that Horizon Europe have, projects developed for encouraging citizen centred initiatives are seen as having a limited impact. With the NEB programme aiming at encouraging small and medium scale citizen engagement projects, the absorption of direct funds is not the main challenge but rather the long-term sustainability of the incentivized initiative. In order to maintain and enhance outcomes, measures must be taken both horizontally for coherence across member states and vertically in order to fill in the gap that was identified by participants regarding the visibility of the programme in the middle segment of the population, that represents the largest part of the envisioned stakeholders of the NEB.

○ 2.3 Digital Skills, Education and learning

- The educational sector faces particular challenges. Uptake of novel technologies puts a pressure on lecturers to acquire the knowledge needed in order to embed the technology in their teachings. Digital solutions are intensively used in the education sector, but traditional learning, with analogue solutions is considered essential for the development of critical thinking in the architecture and built environment programmes. Even if digital skills are faster acquired by the younger population, this comes with a warning from the educator's side on the dangers that lack of critical thinking might bring with itself. Analogue learning has a forming experience.
- Technological transformation has a disruptive effect on organisational structures, ways of working, ways of collaborating, transformations and disruptions accumulate and can have a negative effect on individual levels of saturation regarding new information. This can lead to learning fatigue which again has a negative impact on future learning patterns. This limitation in time and means for accumulation of new skills and knowledge is experience as well in the educational sector, by both students and educators.
- Low levels of literacy of the target population make it difficult to implement digital solutions. The competition with the private sector for digital skills is another challenge that members of the civil society face.
- Knowledge and expertise of digitalization accumulates yearly and thus it is expected that digitalization levels will increase. However, in order to allow for social inclusion and accommodate all digital literacy levels, service providers, public and civic organizations interacting with the general public must also offer analogue solutions.
- Educational programs dedicated to AI are lacking in both volume and levels of adaptation. It is not low literacy in absolute terms that presents the highest risk when it comes to the usage of AI, but rather overreliance on it. Usage of an AI system while not fully understanding how it functions, how its outputs should be interpreted and what the limitations of the technology are can make users overconfident in its results, and as such put them at a higher risk that they were not having used the technology at all. It is that more important than to have correctly designed literacy programmes, addressed to specific target groups and in the case of deployers with legal obligations under the AI Act, also have evaluation activities included in the training programme in order to make sure that the required knowledge and understanding were internalised.
- The need for critical thinking and questioning of the AI enabled output should be an essential part of AI literacy programmes. Two particular groups were identified as requiring special attention, for different reasons. The first category is represented by the young users. They do not have enough critical thinking skills and often do not question the results given by the AI system. The second category is that of senior users who, on the one hand, might have low overall digital literacy and on the other hand a tendency to over rely (in terms of areas of applicability) on the technology because of lack of full understanding of it. AI usage has side effects on critical and creative thinking.
- The subject of critical thinking skills came up during several focus groups, not only in relation to the use of AI solutions but also in relation of other digital technologies. Use of a digital solution should not be in itself a learning objective. Rather, this skill must be developed in a

contextualized learning experience, where inputs, outputs and process are analysed in a critical manner both in their singularity and their intersectionality. Critical thinking skills thus require more time and resources, since an extra layer of complexity is added by the coming of age of the digital. Especially in the educational sector, in the case of young individuals, digital consumption without critical knowledge can be additionally risky, with the potential of the creation of a distorted world image, seen only through the filter of the digital. From a helicopter view, this aggregated phenomenon can lead to risk accumulation, in the form of potential for being victim to disinformation or misinformation, technological dependencies or strategic dependencies.

- Conducting “failure workshops” or “post-mortems” can contribute towards resilience and digital maturity.

○ 2.4 Digitalisation, the Green Deal objectives and Bio-based materials

- The relation between the green and the digital transition is recognized, although not without criticism.
- Political changes at the national level within the EU also have an impact on how the objectives of the Green Deal and sustainability targets are prioritized. The Green Deal is also influenced by changing political agendas or election results of states from outside the EU, whose influence is exercised globally across a multitude of fields, such as the US and China. In order to be able to counterbalance these pressures, participants consider that the European Union must stand out and use its collective weight and critical economic mass that we are offering.
- The NEB priorities are connected to economic growth and the green transition needs to be integrated in this economic growth approach in order to receive support. Adaptation of the language to the target audience is a reality streaming from the political stage: “in the neoliberal context, we bring in this sort of economic argument for a green transition”.
- Within Horizon Europe the green transition is facilitated, even if tangentially, through projects addressing its objectives, such as those around green spaces and urban environments with the extra benefit that collaboration in consortia makes it easier to become aware of the status quo of the implementation of the green deal objectives in different member states and also globally. However, project level initiatives are ephemerally lived and perceived as rather research activities that are disengaged from the real work environment.
- Legislation can be a push factor for digitalisation, as obligations on reporting emissions rates forces the adoption of digital solutions.
- While digitalisation is designed to facilitate reaching the objective of the Green Deal, new technology in itself increases pollution and energy consumption.
- A shared definition of what green means is needed in order to agree if it is defined as “technologically green or in the direction of degrowth”. The green goals are also affected by “all the destruction that is going on now [i.e. in Ukraine]” and can lead to a testing bed for the reconstruction that will follow and how reconstruction can be done differently.
- Policy makers and project developers should not automatically presume that bio-based materials will be embraced by users whenever given the opportunity, only based on the argument of reaching the sustainability objectives, as there are adjacent factors influencing the perception of these alternative materials. Results show that bio-based materials are not viewed uniformly across the investigated landscape. Therefore, initiatives promoting the use of bio-based materials should not start with the premise of direct uptake of these materials but should rather also look into adjacent factors that might induce biased resistance and address those in specific measures.
- Sustainability is perceived as influenced by cultural factors and initiatives for enabling it, such as the perception of bio-based materials is influenced by contextualised consumption, an example being that constructing in wood is associated with low income in some countries. Arguably this is associated also with levels of economic development, tradition of

building and local and national history of the build environment.

- There is a (perceived) gap on knowledge and training on the use of bio-based materials.
- There is a reticence from the client side in accepting the use of bio-based materials (due to costs, durability reasons) if not supported by (at least) aesthetic arguments.
- The lack of standards brings additional challenges for insurance purposes, adding to the reticence of acceptance. Therefore, initiatives for encouraging use of bio-based materials don't have to be limited to financial ones, but can also include initiatives for simplifying regulatory processes.
- Economic growth is enabled by reducing or optimizing expenditures, not only by stimulating growth, and this is particularly relevant for decarbonisation and sustainability measures. Economic growth can be helped by reducing expenditures on transportation of materials or construction and having shorter supply chains. Relating predominantly to quantitative measures of economic growth has been criticised as not providing a comprehensive view over the available measures to stimulate growth. Participants thus suggested taking into consideration other indicators such as self-reliance, biobased materials, locally sourced materials, reducing transportation etc.

○ 2.5 Reflections on the DigiNEB collection

Respondents appreciated the collection of tools for design presented on the DigiNEB project website. As mentioned in Deliverable 3.4 – Early adopters network, national and regional adaptation - during the Digital Focus Groups, participants manifested increased interest in the content of the DigiNEB website and the collection of resources and digital solutions, asking whether the collection is finalised or still growing and also wanted to know when the reports of the research activity will be ready and if they will be disseminated with a wider audience.

The challenge, as reported by one participant, is not in the existing tools or the lack of thereof but rather in finding the right person with the skills needed to use them in the right way. Time is an important factor since project have strict deadlines, therefore sometimes “it’s a gamble to find the right person that can implement it in a fast way”.

Reflecting on the collection provided by the DigiNEB project, in a vein similar to that expressed in the DFG on bio-based materials, respondents from the focus group on digital solutions mention that a quality evaluation method or instrument to ease choice would be welcome in order to save time as “we can’t find our way around easily”. A quality filter enabling choice of digital solutions is what end users and organisations need.

The democracy digital solutions included on the DigiNEB project website were referenced in particular as being appreciated but lacking criteria for choice: “democracy technologies [...] - there's a lot available, but even if I start reading [through] all the tools, I don't know how to [choose]. It feels like another library with a lot of information and I don't know what makes sense or not. It's also something we can't find our way around easily.”

What seems to be missing at the moment is an instrument for enabling choice of adequate digital solution. Similar feedback included: “that's a lot of great tools. How do I translate that so that it becomes impactful for my work or for the goals of my organization? [...] The soft skill part of that is currently underestimated and would require more attention”.

○ 2.6 Looking into the future: NEB prioritises and Impact of the geopolitical context

- Respondents did agree that the geopolitical context has an impact on the NEB priorities: “I'm confident that geopolitics will change the way that new European Bauhaus is structured. Participants acknowledged the current geopolitical context and the energy dependencies pose a threat to the energy security and the green transition.
- With initiatives aimed at reaching the green objectives and obtaining strategic autonomy the way in which the EU will position itself in relation to these geopolitical competitors must be a strategical choice.
- With de-risking being seen as more feasible than de-coupling, economic experts looking at the global impact of a possible economic war between the US and China (The Peterson Institute for International Economics, 2024) now also discuss the possibility of sector de-coupling.

● 3.3 Final remarks and recommendations

Awareness of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) programme is low within the general population, as reported by participants in the Digital Focus Groups. For existing NEB projects, it is difficult to connect both with the NEB programme and with other types of programmes. If the initial NEB civic engagement projects were meant as seed investments, the medium to long term sustainability of the initiatives must be further incentivized. NEB initiatives are perceived as scattered, small scale and short lived. As such, there is no coherent or impactful NEB presence in the wider civic community. In the professional community the NEB brings value as it supports research or development initiatives, but these initiatives most often than not are not wider recognized as being part of the NEB or remain at the level of project reporting.

Should the NEB have the ambition to become a successful programme of the European Commission it needs a cohesive, visible and long-term sustainable approach, where medium to large scale initiatives are facilitated and small-scale initiatives are brought together in an umbrella approach that gives coherence to them as a whole and in the same time makes this coherence visible to both participants and the outside community. With the new commission still forming, the new priorities of the NEB programme as they are proposed in intermediate policies are also little known and uncertain. The tensions streaming from discussions influenced by changing political agendas and potential redirecting of funds from the Green Deal to defence spending bring additional questions regarding the future and relevance of the New European Bauhaus Programme, unless it receives a visibility nudge.

Some of these aspects find their way into official policy programmes. However, there is a sense of less cohesion when it comes to bottom-up perspectives. Again, this can have different causes, such as the fragmented European landscape regarding levels of digitalisation, patterns of consumption against different economic and infrastructure backdrops. With no strong top to bottom connection and ways of convincing end beneficiaries or users of the benefits of different initiatives in cohesive approaches, and with the overarching perspective not visible in a time efficient manner, financial instruments and initiatives meant to reach European wide objectives risk facing bottom – up criticism and pushback.

The NEB programme envisions enhancing civic participation and engagement and in order to do so aims to interact with the citizens by means of novel digital solutions, such as AI or VR.

While focusing on increasing digitalization levels and adopting innovative solutions, we should not turn digitalization in the main goal of NEB. Even if digitalization brings with itself numerous advantages, it is not a requirement per se, just as AI should not be used just for AI's sake. The starting point should always be the target group a certain programme or initiative is meant for, and the methods used to reach the objective of the initiative in relation to that target group should be adopted accordingly.

Closing the innovation gap is on the EU agenda (European Commission, 2024 b.) and plans to do so include actions to stimulate science, technology and innovation. While the risk of overdependency turning into vulnerability is acknowledged at policy level, discussions within the professional NEB community do not naturally lead to such conclusions, unless specifically addressed (as detailed in the section dedicated to the focus group on digital solutions).

Similar to the case of AI, so too in the broader area of digitalisation, there is a power imbalance between decision makers and consumers of digital solutions. The decision makers, whether it is a public authority, research institution, or commercial service provider deploy the technology and the user, whether it is citizen/user or client makes use of the solution without a meaningful dialogue

regarding the choice. Despite the fact that uptake of technology and increased literacy has been associated with empowerment and democratizing processes, the power of decision still lies with the deployers. A different paradox should be noted here. Both public and private entities deploying technological solutions pride themselves with user engagement pre-deployment activities, publicly disseminating the results of these “human or user centric” initiatives, focusing on ethics, respecting transparency, CSR and so on. This difference in perception might arise from the visibility of these initiatives within the certain target groups.

Decarbonisation efforts remain part of the new Commissions’ programme (2024 b.), being the second pillar in the Competitiveness Compass. After 5 years from the start of the programme, and despite received criticism, the Green Deal remains a priority of the European Commission, with a refocus on agile and stimulating the industry sector. While criticism of the Green Deal has been previously made public in media outlets, together with talk of redirecting funds to other current priority areas such as defence, this presumed conflict of priorities was not reported as being known within the community. Additionally, both topics are represented in the three pillars of the new Competitiveness Compass of the European Commission (2024 b.): innovation, decarbonisation and security.

While differences between different global markets have been acknowledged, such as the US market focus on competition, the EU focus on regulation and the China focus on government driven technological innovation, the innovation gap between the EU and these other two global market leaders has not been a subject of attention during the discussion.

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• Annex I. Miro board outputs

Output DFG NEB prize winners and civic engagement

Output DFG NEB focus on education and training

Output workshop Deconstructing AI Literacy

Template for comparative AI literacy needs evaluation for 3 roles: developer; deployer and affected person/ citizen

DEVELOPER	Your Role/Organisation sector	DEPLOYER	Your Role/Organisation sector	CITIZEN (AFFECTED PERSON)	Your Role/Organisation sector
<p>Dangers of low AI literacy</p> <p>Type something</p>	<p>Main literacy content:</p> <p>Knowledge about: Type something</p> <p>Skills: Type something</p> <p>Understanding of: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge of risks of AI development: Type something</p>	<p>Dangers of low AI literacy</p> <p>Type something</p>	<p>Main literacy content:</p> <p>Knowledge about: Type something</p> <p>Skills: Type something</p> <p>Understanding of: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge of risks of AI development: Type something</p>	<p>Dangers of low AI literacy</p> <p>Type something</p>	<p>Main literacy content:</p> <p>Knowledge about: Type something</p> <p>Skills: Type something</p> <p>Understanding of: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI: Type something</p> <p>Knowledge of risks of AI development: Type something</p>
<p>Literacy Level</p> <p>Rate the required literacy level</p> <p>Governance of AI: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Fundamental rights: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Privacy and data protection: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Contract management: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Sustainability: 1 2 3 4 5</p>	<p>Literacy Level</p> <p>Rate the required literacy level</p> <p>Foundations of AI (technical): 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Technical aspects and safety: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Data: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Risk and non-discrimination: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Legislation relating to AI: 1 2 3 4 5</p>	<p>Literacy Level</p> <p>Rate the required literacy level</p> <p>Governance of AI: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Fundamental rights: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Privacy and data protection: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Contract management: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Sustainability: 1 2 3 4 5</p>	<p>Literacy Level</p> <p>Rate the required literacy level</p> <p>Foundations of AI (technical): 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Technical aspects and safety: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Data: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Risk and non-discrimination: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Legislation relating to AI: 1 2 3 4 5</p>	<p>Literacy Level</p> <p>Rate the required literacy level</p> <p>Governance of AI: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Fundamental rights: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Privacy and data protection: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Contract management: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Sustainability: 1 2 3 4 5</p>	<p>Literacy Level</p> <p>Rate the required literacy level</p> <p>Foundations of AI (technical): 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Technical aspects and safety: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Data: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Risk and non-discrimination: 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p>Legislation relating to AI: 1 2 3 4 5</p>

Detailed view on the evaluation form of AI literacy needs for the developer role.

DEVELOPER

Your Role/Organisation sector

Dangers of low AI literacy

Type something

Main literacy content:

Knowledge about

Skills

Understanding of:

Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI

Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI.

Knowledge of risks of AI development

Literacy Level
Rate the required literacy level

Governance of AI

Fundamental rights

Privacy and data protection

Contract management

Sustainability

Literacy Level
Rate the required literacy level

Foundations of AI [technical]

Technical aspects and safety

Data

Bias and non-discrimination

Legislation relating to AI

Output Digital Focus Group Bio-Based materials

Enablers of technological innovation are:

Examples of initiatives for increasing the re-use and re-purposing of materials, building elements, buildings and public spaces towards circularity in construction, based on reversible building design and sufficiency.

Examples of innovative bio-based regenerative construction materials for structural and exterior architecture.

Examples of innovative supply chains - taking the cascading principle - that transform waste materials into high-quality secondary construction materials and products.

The following digitalisation needs should be prioritized:

Examples of innovative use of by-products and secondary bio-based materials (including reclaimed wood)

The main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe are:

Examples of social, aesthetic, and economic impacts of carbon-sequestering materials in the built environment.

Other factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe:

- Annex II. Overview of input on the AI literacy content for three different roles: Developer/ Deployer/ Citizen (affected persons)

AI literacy skills	Developers	Deployers	Citizens (affected persons)
Knowledge about	GPU and energy use; Hallucination detection; Dilution aspects; Developing AI models; Processing demands; Development methodology; Programming languages etc.	How systems scale; How to maximize GPU usage; How to protect customer data; How to measure performance; Governance, test; Ongoing system maintenance and updates, System performance in real-world scenarios.	Knowing the weaknesses of the technologies and their uses; Ability to integrate AI and "conventional" approaches; Understanding of implications and limits; How the tech works, and what is possible. How to critical think; Privacy and security risks.
Skills:	Machine Learning operations Fine-tune of models LÖRA's Machine Learning and deep learning algorithms. Development skills for the proper development environment	Semantic analysis; Machine learning and deep learning models, LLM.	Foundational knowledge in the discipline, critical thinking, common sense; Critical thinking, reasoning, general computer literacy; Knowledge to evaluate and challenge; Critical thinking.
Understanding of:	How to read and analyse existing research papers and implement them Implementation frameworks, system constraints. Legislation, ethical aspects, user requirements. etc.	Sectors and how they [work]; Legislation, explainability.	Discipline area, risks stemming from heavily filtered materials, censorship; Biases; How the tools work, how they can upskill you, or improve your career prospects; Discipline area, risks stemming from heavily filtered materials, censorship; Biases; Legislation; Ethical aspects.

Knowledge and understanding of Societal good of AI include:	How industries might use your system to benefit their growth or increase revenue.	Efficiency, accessibility.	Understanding of multiplier effects theories, lowering of friction, interface training; Can improve work/live balance, increased economic power and efficiency.
Knowledge and understanding of Societal harm of AI:	How systems can be jailbroken; How systems can be manipulated; Technology wars; How biased data affect results; Algorithmic Bias; Deepfakes and Misinformation.	Equipping bad actors to inflict harm; Manipulation and dissemination of false, harmful, or few content; Unwarranted; Incorrect citizen data (credit score, health, identification, etc).	Mandatory - multiplier effect once again; Anger, harm violence, defamation.
Knowledge of risks of AI development:	How systems can be jailbroken; How to gracefully handle misinformation and biases; How to set up systems to monitor outputs; Societal bias in outputs; Use of KPIs to detect anomalies; [are] Important.	No clear problem to be solved; Turning the internet into a dumpster; Intensive knowledge; Transparency.	Societal impact vs. defined risk outputs; Language is important, proper wording mandatory (legal); How companies can be manipulated, costs of services, how to think critically.

Output DFG NEB focus on Digital Solutions – architecture, Parametric and digital design, BIM/Digital twins.

Digital Technical Working Digital Solutions - Architecture, Parametric and digital design, BIM/ Digital twins.

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Enablers of technological innovation in my sector are:

The following digitalisation needs should be prioritized in our sector:

The main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe are:

Other factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe:

● Annex III. TDWG questionnaires

○ Digital Focus Group questionnaire

■ Verticals– NEB prize winners -

Introduction on the activity: Focus on digitalisation;NEB priorities

Intro participants.

Block 1:

- What is the level of digitalisation within your profession?
- What are the main challenges when it comes to using the available digital solutions?
- What digital solution is most needed at the moment in your field?
- In what measure are AI technologies used in your sector? / How are technologies such as artificial intelligence or virtual reality used in order to involve citizens in decision-making processes?
- Are there enough incentives to stimulate innovation in your sector?

Block 2: MIRO

Enablers of technological innovation in my sector are:

The main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe:

- the growth of a circular and regenerative construction,
- the green transition,
- the digital transformation,
- measures for increasing resilience, competitiveness,
- measures for increasing inclusiveness and democracy.

The following digitalisation needs should be prioritized in our sector:

- recruiting,
- archiving
- communication
- Clustered solutions allowing for creation of personalized unique functional work context and for tool combination
- Platforms allowing collaboration on projects from any device with access to all project documents, contracts, RFIs, submittals, schedules, drawings and more/
- Material Passports /
- Advanced Materials/
- Open:

Block 3. Closing questions:

- What are the digital skills needed for the realization of the objectives of the New European Bauhaus?
- What should be the priorities of the future New European Bauhaus programme?
- What impact has the NEB prize had on your career?

- Digital Focus Group questionnaire

- Verticals – Education and training -

Introduction on the activity: Focus on digitalisation; NEB priorities

Intro participants.

Block 1:

- In what way does digitalisation contribute to the targets of the NEB programme / Green Deal?
- What are the digital skills needed for the realization of the objectives of the New European Bauhaus? [What are **the gaps** in the skills needed to reach the NEB objectives?] [test for AI literacy].
- What digital solution is most needed at the moment?
- What are the gaps in the learning resources needed to reach the NEB objectives? What actions can be undertaken in order to address these gaps?
- What are the main challenges when it comes to using the available digital solutions for training and developing of skills?
- How are innovative models used for strengthening education and skilling in line with industry and SMEs requirements?
- How are technologies such as artificial intelligence or virtual reality used in order to involve citizens in the design and decision-making processes?
- Are TRL levels of innovative products such as user-centric services and digital platforms well suited for effective citizen engagement?

Block 2: MIRO

The main platform used for training and developing of skills is:

The strengths and weaknesses of tools and projects focussing on training and skills are:

The following digitalisation needs should be prioritized in order to reach the NEB objectives:

What online platforms facilitating citizen participation do you know? What other functions should these platforms have?

Main factors for the open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe are:

- the green transition,
- the digital transformation,
- measures for increasing resilience, competitiveness, inclusiveness and democracy.

Other factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe are:

Block 3. Closing questions:

- In your opinion, what impact will the current geopolitical context have on the NEB priorities? [horizon scanning]
- How has the Horizon Europe programme facilitated collaboration with industry for reaching the objectives of the Green Deal?
- In Horizon Europe are the TRLs targets well adapted to the achievements of the foreseen Green Deal goal?
- What should be the priorities of the future New European Bauhaus programme?

- Digital Focus Group questionnaire
 - AI for societal good/ AI literacy

Questions addressed via Menti Menter:

- What does trustworthy AI mean to you? [cloud word]
- Based on which criteria do you choose a certain AI application? [open ended answer]
- The main risks relating to AI are [open ended answer]
- Human centric AI is about [open ended answer]
- Main adverse impacts of AI systems on society are: [open ended answer]
- The paramount factor when choosing to deploy an AI application should be: [word cloud]
- The European approach to Artificial Intelligence means: [open ended answer]

- Digital Focus Group questionnaire

- Production and construction – Bio – Based materials

Introduction on the activity: Focus on digitalisation; NEB priorities

Intro participants.

Block 1:

- What are the main challenges when it comes to using the available digital solutions within your field?/What digital solution is most needed at the moment in your field?
- In what measure does the current state of digitalisation in your sector contribute to the targets of the Green Deal?
- What should be prioritized in the European Green Deal? (Bio- based materials – connected to the targets of the Green Deal).
- How is artificial intelligence used for making the regenerative construction more affordable?
- How are market dynamics, incentives, risks, and barriers affecting the adoption of more circular and sustainable building practices?
- What non-economic factors trigger investors to cover costs associated with sustainable, regenerative and inclusive construction projects and to overcome the perceived risks?
- What initiatives should be implemented for better collection, structuring, processing and use of data to increase circularity in buildings?
- What are good practices of regenerative designs for buildings and public spaces?
- What are the principal needs of your sector /industry/ in order to become more sustainable and decarbonise?
- Are current financing opportunities well equipped to address the needs of SMEs in their decarbonisation efforts?

Block 2: MIRO

Main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness in Europe by encouraging the growth of a circular and regenerative construction:

The green transition,

- digital transformation,
- measures for increasing resilience, competitiveness, inclusiveness and democracy.

Enablers of technological innovation are:

Examples of innovative bio-based regenerative construction materials for structural and exterior architecture.

Examples of innovative supply chains – taking the cascading principle - that transform waste materials into high-quality secondary construction materials and products.

Examples of social, aesthetic, and economic impacts of carbon-sequestering materials in the built environment.

Examples of innovative use of by-products and secondary bio-based materials (including re-claimed wood).

Examples of initiatives for increasing the re-use and re-purposing of materials, building elements, buildings and public spaces towards circularity in construction, based on reversible building design and sufficiency.

Block 3. Closing questions:

- What should be the priorities of the future New European Bauhaus programme?
- What would be appropriate strategies for meaningful community engagement in the design and construction process?
- In what ways can community engagement be enhanced in the design and construction process through the use of digital platforms and emerging technologies?
- How are technologies such as artificial intelligence or virtual reality used in order to involve citizens in decision-making processes?
- In Horizon Europe are the TRLs targets well adapted to the achievements of the foreseen Green Deal goal?

- Digital Focus Group questionnaire

- Design & Architecture – Digital Solutions - Parametric and digital design, BIM/ Digital twins

Introduction on the activity: Focus on digitalisation; NEB priorities – 5 min.

Intro participants.

Block 1:

- What is the level of digitalisation within your profession?
- What are the main challenges when it comes to using [the available] digital solutions? [testing for elements identified in the preliminary gap analysis]. / What is a current gap in the digitalisation needs in your sector? [testing for skills/instruments/policies etc].
- What digital solution is most needed at the moment in your field?/ What digital solutions would users like to have that are not available at the moment?
- Are there enough incentives to stimulate innovation in your sector?
- What are the education needs in your sector?
- To what extent do you believe technological innovation could make your business/sector more sustainable?
- What are the best incentives for digitalisation uptake in your sector?
- What are the main impediments for digitalisation uptake [in your sector]?
- In what measure are AI technologies used in your sector?
- How are technologies such as artificial intelligence or virtual reality used in order to involve citizens in the design and decision-making processes?

Block 2. - Miro board exercise prompts:

[List/give examples of] Enablers of technological innovation .

The digitalisation needs that should be prioritized.

Main factors for open strategic autonomy and competitiveness by encouraging the growth of a circular and regenerative construction in Europe:

- the green transition,
- digital transformation,
- measures for increasing European resilience, competitiveness, inclusiveness and democracy.

Block 3: Closing questions:

- In what measure does the current state of digitalisation in your sector contribute to the targets of the Green Deal?
- What should be the priorities of the future New European Bauhaus programme?
- In your view, what impact will the current geopolitical context have on the NEB priorities?

